

Improvements of the CFB-CaL system integrated with CPU: sensitivity analysis of main CaL parameters

Deliverable D4.4

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D4.4 Improvements of the CFB-CaL system integrated with CPU: sensitivity analysis of main CaL parameters

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1 INTRODUCTION

Deliverable D4.4 focuses on improved configurations of the CFB-CaL system integrated with CPU. Process modelling activities were carried out, analyzing several plant configurations and varying some operating parameters, with the aim of increasing CO₂ capture rates (i.e., up to 99%, and enabling even negative emissions in case of waste/biomass co-firing in the calciner), improving energy efficiency and reducing CO₂ avoided costs. In cooperation with Task 4.1, this deliverable analyzes the effect of several process improvement options: (i) carbonator outlet temperature reduction; (ii) strategies to preheat the sorbent delivered to the CaL calciner; (iii) injection of a Ca(OH)₂ polishing stream after the carbonator; (iv) use of O₂ generated as by-product from electrolysis in the oxyfuel calciner; (v) maximization of the CO₂ capture efficiency by recycling the CPU vent gas to the carbonator.¹

2 DESCRIPTION OF REFERENCE PLANTS

This section describes the reference cement, waste-to-energy, bio-CHP and steel plants where the CaL system is applied in its base and advanced configuration².

2.1 Reference cement plant

The reference cement plant without CO₂ capture is based on the Best Available Techniques (BAT), as defined in the European BREF Document for cement manufacturing (Kourti et al., 2013). Its model was developed within the framework of the CEMCAP project (Anantharaman et al., 2018; Campanari et al., 2016).

The reference cement kiln has a production capacity up to 3000 t/d of clinker (assuming a raw meal-to-clinker conversion factor of 1.6), representative of a typical European cement plant. This corresponds to an annual clinker production of approximately 1 Mt, assuming an operational period exceeding 330 days per year. Based on an average clinker-to-cement ratio of 0.737, the annual cement production is estimated at 1.36 Mt. Considering a capacity utilization factor of 91.5%, the total CO₂ emissions at the stack for this plant, employing 100% coal as the fuel and operating without Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS), amount to approximately 850 kt_{CO2}/y.

As illustrated in Figure 1, raw materials (see Table 1 for composition) are ground and dried through direct contact with hot gases from the preheater tower and subsequently preheated in a five-stage cyclone preheater via direct contact with counterflowing process gases. The dust-laden gases used in the drying and grinding processes in the raw mill are separated from entrained solids via a cyclone and a fabric filter before being released to the stack.

The kiln feed enters the pre-calciner, where the majority of calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) and magnesium carbonate (MgCO₃) undergo calcination, forming calcium oxide (CaO), magnesium oxide (MgO), and CO₂. The calcination degree, defined as the molar ratio of CaO to total Ca at the pre-calciner outlet, is approximately 94%. The thermal energy required for calcination is supplied by coal combustion, with the coal composition and lower heating value detailed in Table 2. Tertiary air from the clinker cooler, at a temperature of 1050°C, is employed for combustion in the pre-calciner. An in-line calciner configuration is adopted, whereby the rotary kiln off-gas, at 1078°C, is introduced into the pre-calciner.

¹ Further refinement of the existing models is planned for the next deliverable of the project (D4.5, “Optimal full-scale CFB-CaL+CPU configurations for each industrial sector”).

² The reference plants are the same considered in the previous deliverable D4.3 (“Base cases definition and KPIs calculation for cement, steel, Bio-CHP and WtE plants with and without capture”).

The rotary kiln constitutes the core of clinker production, facilitating the final stages of calcination and the formation of clinker phases. The hot clinker advances toward the kiln’s high-temperature zone, where coal combustion occurs. Combustion air is supplied from the clinker cooler (secondary air), as well as from primary air. Post-combustion, the flue gases move counter-currently toward the pre-calciner, while the solid phase progresses toward the kiln burner, where clinker phase formation takes place. The hot clinker reaches a peak temperature of approximately 1450°C at the kiln outlet before being discharged to the clinker cooler.

In the clinker cooler, rapid cooling minimizes the formation of undesirable coarse crystals and prevents the dissociation of alite (C_3S , $3CaO \cdot SiO_2$) into belite (C_2S , $2CaO \cdot SiO_2$) and free lime (CaO).

The clinker composition shown in Table 3 is simplified, but sufficient for mass and energy balance calculations. A more detailed composition describing the mineralogical phase distribution is not considered by the model as this level of detail is beyond the scope of this study and not necessary to evaluate the performance of the capture process.

Figure 1: Schematic of the reference cement burning process without CCS.

Table 1: Raw material composition.

Species	Unit of measurement	Composition
CaCO ₃	% _{wt}	79.08
SiO ₂	% _{wt}	13.77
Al ₂ O ₃	% _{wt}	3.33
Fe ₂ O ₃	% _{wt}	2.01
MgCO ₃	% _{wt}	1.53
Moisture	% _{wt}	0.28

Table 2: Coal composition and heating value.

Species	Unit of measurement	Composition
C - Carbon	% _{wt}	69.00
H - Hydrogen	% _{wt}	4.00
S - Sulphur	% _{wt}	0.50
N - Nitrogen	% _{wt}	0.48
O - Oxygen	% _{wt}	9.00
Ash	% _{wt}	16.50
Moisture	% _{wt}	0.50
LHV - Lower Heating Value	MJ/kg	27.15

Table 3: Clinker composition.

Species	Unit of measurement	Composition
C3S	% _{wt}	63.26
C2S	% _{wt}	13.75
C3A	% _{wt}	10.79
C4AF	% _{wt}	9.85
CaO	% _{wt}	0.79
CaSO ₄	% _{wt}	0.38
MgO	% _{wt}	1.18

2.2 Reference waste to energy and bio-CHP plants

The reference Waste-to-Energy (WtE) plant refers to a generic modern European WtE as described in the BAT report (Neuwahl et al., 2019). The plant provides electricity and thermal heat through the city's district heating network to the nearby metropolitan area. The schematic of the WtE plant is depicted in Figure 2.

The plant is composed of two grate-based combustion lines, each with its own dedicated flue-gas treatment section, treating a total of 700 kt of Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) per year. The two grate boilers are designed for a thermal power of 121.5 MW_{th} each, corresponding to an hourly throughput of about 43.75 t/h of MSW. The plant is expected to operate for 8000 equivalent hours per year, corresponding to a capacity factor of 91.3%. The properties of the MSW burnt in the reference plant are resumed in Table 4. The heat released during the combustion process is recovered under the form of superheated steam, to be valorized in the steam cycle of the plant, featuring a steam turbine with nominal gross electric power of 78 MW_{el}.

The flue gas treatment section features: injection of hydrated lime and activated carbon for the abatement of heavy metals, a bag filter to separate the injected solids, a Selective Catalytic Reactor (SCR) and a Wet Scrubber (WS) that is used to meet SO₂ and acid gas emissions limit.

Figure 2: Schematic of WtE plant with district heating.

The **Bio-CHP** plant taken as reference in this project is managed by Grupo HUNOSA and is a CFB-based combustion boiler originally deputed to burn locally sourced coal, later adapted to accept waste biomass co-combustion and now undergoing a retrofit to accept 100% biomass feed. The properties of the wood pellet that will be burnt in the plant are reported Table 4. The fuel requirements make it compatible with the ENplus A1 category. Also for the Bio-CHP plant, 8000 equivalent working hours per year have been assumed.

Table 4: Properties of the design MSW of the reference WtE and properties of the wood pellet for the Bio-CHP case.

	Unit of measurement	MSW composition	Wood pellet composition
C - Carbon	% _{wt}	26.42	48.80
H - Hydrogen	% _{wt}	3.68	5.70
N - Nitrogen	% _{wt}	0.47	0.06
O - Oxygen	% _{wt}	19.05	41.20
S - Sulphur	% _{wt}	0.16	0.008
Cl - Chlorine	% _{wt}	0.45	0.006
Ash	% _{wt}	16.00	0.40
Humidity	% _{wt}	33.76	3.80
LHV - Lower Heating Value	MJ/kg	10.00	18.54

In Table 5 the main performance of both WtE and Bio-CHP reference plants are reported.

Table 5: WtE and Bio-CHP KPIs for full electric operating mode.

	Unit of measurement	WtE	Bio-CHP
Type of fuel	-	Municipal Solid Waste	Wood pellet
Nominal thermal input	MW _{th}	243.1	135.3
Fuel consumption	t/y - TJ _{LHV} /y	700000 - 7000	210000 - 3896
Gross electricity production	MW - MWh/y	77.0 - 616000	43.4 - 347000
Gross electric efficiency	%	31.68	32.08
Net electricity production	MW - MWh/y	70.0 - 560000	39.1 - 313000
Net electric efficiency	%	28.80	28.90
CO ₂ emissions	t/y - kg/t _{fuel} - kg/GJ _{fuel}	673000 - 961.90 - 96.19	282000 - 1343 - 72.38

2.3 Reference steel plant

The reference plant for the Steel case is an Electric Arc Furnace (EAF) owned by Celsa Nordic and located in Mo I Rana, Norway, with a nominal production capacity of 112 t/h of liquid steel. In the general EAF process, the feedstock (mainly scrap) is melted at elevated temperatures (1700-1800°C) by the supply of electricity through electrodes. Besides, other materials, such as anthracite, oxygen, calcium oxide, and dolomite are added to control the process chemistry and composition of produced steel. The nominal consumptions of the EAF plant are reported in Table 6. The flue gases considered for this work were measured at the plant. The schematic diagram of the system, indicating the measurement points, is presented in Figure 3. The measurements were made at different positions. At position 1, located in the scrap pre-heating duct, the gas temperature and contents of CO, CO₂, H₂, and O₂ were measured. Volume flow rate and dust load were measured at position 2 after the post-combustion zone; while the properties measured at position 3 were gas temperature and contents of H₂O, CO, CO₂, O₂, NH₃, NO_x, CH₄, etc. The ranges for each property and average values are reported in Table 7.

Table 6. Reference EAF feed, electricity, and anthracite consumption (information about scrap and fuel consumption was not available). Data provided by Swerim AB

	Unit of measurement	Value
Carbon addition (anthracite)	kg/t _{steel}	8
Electrode consumption	kg/t _{steel}	5
Oxygen	Nm ³ /h	3 000 - 5 000
Electricity	MW	50 - 70
Calcium oxide	kg/t _{steel}	22.6
Dolomite	kg/t _{steel}	17.8
CO₂ emissions		
Total CO ₂ emitted (capacity factor of 91.3%)	t/y	92133
Specific CO ₂ emissions	t _{CO2} /t _{steel}	0.103

Figure 3: Schematic of the EAF plant with the location of measurement points. Provided by Swerim AB. The post-combustion system is used to control the content of unburned gases by adding air to the hot gases stream. It only operates in periods with high concentrations of unburned gases (e.g., CO, H₂, C_xH_y).

Table 7: Ranges and average value for the flue gas properties measured at the EAF plant on a 15-hours duration period.

Position 1	Unit of measurement	Range	Average
CO	ppm _{vol}	0.03 - 10 197	392
CO ₂	% _{vol, wet basis}	0.01 - 25.44	7.11
H ₂	% _{vol, wet basis}	0.00 - 4.17	0.25
O ₂	% _{vol, wet basis}	0.67 - 21.49	14.67
Temperature	°C	250 - 1 197	678
Position 2	Unit of measurement	Range	Average
Volume flow rate	Nm ³ /h	1954 - 356 798	151 391
Position 3	Unit of measurement	Range	Average
CO	ppm _{vol}	0.11 - 7303.96	447.41
CO ₂	% _{vol, wet basis}	0.08 - 10.00	3.02
H ₂ O	% _{vol, wet basis}	0.52 - 12.90	4.27
O ₂	% _{vol, wet basis}	11.11 - 23.16	17.37
N ₂ O	ppm _{vol}	0.0 - 1.76	0.24
NO	ppm _{vol}	0.01 - 351.43	18.52
NO ₂	ppm _{vol}	0.01 - 17.68	1.66
NH ₃	ppm _{vol}	0.06 - 17.49	4.21
SO ₂	ppm _{vol}	0.03 - 117.43	4.27
SO ₃	ppm _{vol}	0.01 - 1.08	0.24
HCl	ppm _{vol}	0.01 - 4.49	0.52
HF	ppm _{vol}	1.37 - 53.06	10.00
HCN	ppm _{vol}	0.01 - 13.65	2.50
CH ₄	ppm _{vol}	0.01 - 195.86	12.06
C ₂ H ₆	ppm _{vol}	0.01 - 20.41	3.04
C ₂ H ₄	ppm _{vol}	0.01 - 445.25	8.64
C ₃ H ₈	ppm _{vol}	0.01 - 3.93	0.63
C ₆ H ₁₄	ppm _{vol}	0.10 - 11.24	2.85
CHOH	ppm _{vol}	0.02 - 33.85	7.26
Temperature	°C	100.00 - 421.50	230.21

3 INTEGRATION WITH CALCIUM LOOPING AND SIMULATION ASSUMPTIONS

3.1 CaL for cement plants

Two possible calcium looping integrated configurations were evaluated in D4.3 (“Base cases definition and KPIs calculation for cement, steel, Bio-CHP and WtE plants with and without capture”), each characterized by different raw materials fed to the process: (i) coarse pure limestone and fine raw meal with adequately modified chemical composition, and (ii) coarse raw meal. As the first was deemed more favorable both from economic and technical perspectives, it was selected as the base case for the subsequent analyses. The plant scheme is shown in Figure 4.

Cement plant with integrated CaL-CFB

Figure 4: Simplified process flow diagram of the base CFB-CaL cement plant scheme.

An updated model of this configuration has been built in Aspen Plus to include finer process simulation details, such as more accurate thermo-physical properties of various compounds on broader temperature ranges (particularly for SiO₂), air infiltrations and heat losses. The main simulation assumptions are detailed in Table 8.

The cement plant consists of: a material handling and milling section³, two feed strings with pure limestone and raw material (composition reported in Table 9), each equipped with a two-stage cyclone preheater, a calcium looping

³ In order to provide a comprehensive comparison with the base case, the configuration considered for the material handling and milling section (see Figure 4) has been maintained the same as that presented in the previous report (D4.3) and in the reference work, while keeping also the distribution of different solid flow rates (namely limestone, raw material and recovered CaL purge) across the different preheating lines unchanged. The optimal configuration of the 'milling and preheating section' will be addressed in a later phase of the project, with the goal of optimizing and simplifying the plant operation. Likewise, the

system, a rotary kiln, and a grate clinker cooler (Anantharaman et al., 2018; Campanari et al., 2016). This plant has the same production capacity as the reference plant.

The dried limestone is preheated in a two-stage cyclone through direct contact with CO₂-rich gases from the calciner, while the raw meal is preheated using the kiln's flue gases; a completed calcination of MgCO₃ occurs in this preheating section. Each preheater stage comprises a riser duct, where the gas carries upwards and heats solid particles, and a cyclone, which separates these particles and distributes them to the stage below. The preheated materials are fed into the calciner with the materials coming from the carbonator, and a completed calcination is achieved. The thermal energy required for this calcination reaction is supplied by coal combustion, which is transported to the pre-calciner by a pneumatic system. After the calciner, a selective cyclone determines the distribution of materials between the kiln and the carbonator, based on particle size. In the specific: (i) 99% of the fine material originally coming from the raw material silo is sent to the kiln; (ii) 95% of the coarse calcined material separated by the carbonator cyclone is redirected back to the carbonator for the next CO₂ capture cycle; (iii) the coarse free lime obtained from the fresh limestone feed is equally divided between carbonator and kiln (CaLSR equal to 50% as defined in Table 8 footnote). The calcined material sent to the kiln is mixed with the CaL purge, previously milled and reheated to 750°C using the CO₂-lean gas from the carbonator and the tertiary air (III air). After the rotary kiln, the clinker is cooled to 115°C, while the flue gases are sent to the preheating towers of the raw material and then to the carbonator for the carbon capture.

distribution of various materials along the preheating section will be optimized to enhance the energy efficiency of the process, while minimizing the impact on clinker production costs.

Table 8: Main technical parameters for the reference CaL-CFB cement plant (Anantharaman et al., 2018; Campanari et al., 2016; Kourti et al., 2013).

Technical parameter	Unit of measurement	Value
Reference fuel mix	-	100% coal
Cyclones efficiency (1 st /2 nd /3 rd /4 th stage)	%	96/86/86/86
ASU oxygen purity	%	95.00
Calciner outlet temperature	°C	920.0
Calcination degree at calciner outlet	%	100.0
O ₂ molar fraction at calciner inlet	% _{vol}	39.50
O ₂ molar fraction in calciner off-gas	% _{vol}	3.50
Carbonator outlet temperature	°C	650.0
Temperature of solids out of mills	°C	60.0
Purge re-heating temperature	°C	750.0
Gas temperature at kiln inlet	°C	1078.5
O ₂ molar fraction in kiln off-gas	% _{vol}	2.40
Secondary air to rotary kiln	Nm ³ /t _{clk}	278.38
Tertiary air to purge cyclones	Nm ³ /t _{clk}	629.8
Secondary air temperature	°C	1137.0
Tertiary air temperature	°C	1049.8
Clinker temperature at cooler outlet	°C	114.9
Heat losses from calciner	kJ _{th} /kg _{clk}	95.63
Heat losses from kiln	kJ _{th} /kg _{clk}	180.20
Heat losses from clinker cooler	kJ _{th} /kg _{clk}	11.13
Air infiltration in filters and cyclones	Nm ³ _{air} /Nm ³ _{gas}	0.010
Air infiltration in reactors	Nm ³ _{air} /Nm ³ _{gas}	0.005
CaL split ratio (CaLSR) ^(a)	%	50.00
F _R /F _{CO2}	-	2.987

^(a) CaL split ratio (CaLSR) is defined as the percentage of fresh Ca entering the loop of CaL process with respect to the total Ca fed to the plant as pure limestone.

Table 9: Raw material composition.

Species	Unit of measurement	Raw meal composition
CaCO ₃	% _{wt}	52.67
SiO ₂	% _{wt}	30.82
Al ₂ O ₃	% _{wt}	7.89
Fe ₂ O ₃	% _{wt}	4.76
MgCO ₃	% _{wt}	3.62
Moisture	% _{wt}	0.24

3.2 CaL for waste to energy and bio-CHP plants

The Calcium-Looping system, shown in Figure 5 is integrated into the Waste-to-Energy plant in a tail-end configuration, positioned before the wet scrubber, where the flue gases have a temperature of 120°C. Since it is

expected that the SO₂ co-capture by the CaL sorbent will exceed the target capture level to comply with the environmental regulations, the wet scrubber can be removed.

Table 10: Flue gases at the inlet of the carbonator for the CaL-WtE plant (comprising both combustion lines) and for the CaL-Bio-CHP plant.

	Unit of measurement	WtE-CaL plant	Bio-CHP-CaL plant
Flow rate	Nm ³ /h	452510	138051
Mass flow rate	kg/s	155.25	49.83
Temperature	°C	120.0	150.0
N ₂	% _{vol, wet basis}	65.81	70.20
O ₂	% _{vol, wet basis}	6.67	5.00
CO ₂	% _{vol, wet basis}	9.52	13.05
H ₂ O	% _{vol, wet basis}	18.0	11.75
HCl	ppm _{vol}	10.6	0
SO ₂	ppm _{vol}	7.9	0

The stream entering the CaL section (properties resumed in Table 10) has a flowrate of 450000 Nm³/h, and a CO₂ content of 9.5%. The flue gases enter the carbonator, a Circulating Fluidized Bed (CFB) reactor operated at 650°C, where the CO₂ is captured through the carbonation reaction by the CaO-based sorbent, which is partially converted to CaCO₃. The flowrate of solid sorbent entering the carbonator is proportional to the flowrate of CO₂ (the ratio is fixed by the factor F_R/F_{CO_2}). As the carbonation reaction is exothermic the reactor is cooled down by producing steam. The CO₂-lean flue gases, separated from the solids in the cyclone, leave the carbonator and are routed to the stack at 120°C after the heat recovery section. The solid stream containing CaCO₃ is sent from the carbonator to the calciner for regeneration, which occurs at 920°C and generates a gaseous stream with a high CO₂ concentration. The heat necessary for regeneration is provided by burning fuel under oxyfuel conditions, in order to avoid the dilution of the concentrated CO₂ (released via sorbent calcination) with the N₂ coming from air. The fuel used in the calciner of the WtE-CaL plant is Refuse Derived Fuel (RDF), with an assumed biogenic carbon content of 40% (with respect to the total carbon content) and a LHV of 16600 kJ/kg (Table 11). The CO₂-rich gas leaving the calciner is sent to the heat recovery section. Part of this stream, after being cooled down to 400°C, is recirculated to the carbonator inlet and mixed with oxygen so that the oxidant stream entering the calciner has an O₂ percentage of 40%, while the O₂ percentage at the reactor outlet is 3.55%.

In order to keep the sorbent activity high, a make-up of fresh CaCO₃ is continuously introduced in the calciner, while a purge is extracted, which avoids also the accumulation of ashes coming from the calciner fuel. The make-up is fixed by the ratio F_0/F_{CO_2} . On one hand, high values of this parameter, together with the sorbent excess (F_R/F_{CO_2}) ensure a carbonator higher capture efficiency (i.e., closer to the equilibrium limit value depending on temperature and CO₂ concentration at the inlet). On the other hand, a high F_0/F_{CO_2} is associated with a thermodynamic loss due to the first calcination of CaCO₃, while a high F_R/F_{CO_2} is associated with a higher heat demand at the calciner, as a bigger amount of solids need to be heated to 920°C and then cooled down to 650°C, although this heat is partially recovered through steam production. In order to reach a good compromise between capture efficiency and thermodynamic losses, F_0/F_{CO_2} is fixed to 0.1, while F_R/F_{CO_2} is fixed to 8.

The heat recovered from gas streams leaving the reactors and from the cooling of the carbonator is utilized for superheated steam generation (at 500°C and 60 bar) and oxygen preheating, contributing to the overall energy efficiency of the system. Air infiltrations of 1% mass basis in the boiler and 3% in the bag filters have been assumed, given that the plant is operated at negative pressure. The capture section requires also the installation of an Air

Separation Unit (ASU) to produce the oxygen, and of a purification and compression unit for bringing the CO₂-rich stream released by the calciner to the transport and storage conditions.

Figure 5: Simplified process flow diagram of the CaL system for the WtE plant.

Table 11: Attributes of the RDF to be used in the calciner.

Species	Unit of measurement	Composition
C - Carbon	%wt, as received	43.79
H - Hydrogen	%wt, as received	5.87
N - Nitrogen	%wt, as received	0.33
O - Oxygen	%wt, as received	31.57
S - Sulphur	%wt, as received	0.06
Cl - Chlorine	%wt, as received	0.15
Ash	%wt, as received	3.83
Moisture	%wt, as received	14.41
LHV - Lower Heating Value	kJ/kg	16600

In the **Bio-CHP plant**, the carbonator is fed with the gas before the stack (properties resumed in Table 10). The same high-grade wood pellet used of the Bio-CHP boiler (properties in Table 4) is used as calciner fuel. Being the CO₂ concentration in the flue gases higher than that of the WtE application, lower values of F_0/F_{CO_2} and F_R/F_{CO_2} (0.09 and 7, respectively) are needed to guarantee CO₂ capture efficiency close to the equilibrium value, which provides lower operational costs related to lower fuel and oxygen consumptions. The stack temperature is maintained at the value of the original plant at 150°C.

The general assumptions used for performing the simulations are reported in Table 12 and Table 13⁴. The only noteworthy modification is related to the heat recovery stream cycle to valorize the heat recovered from the CaL system, which in the advanced configurations has been better thermally integrated with the various hot streams and reactors, while in the Base case has remained unvaried.

Table 12: Main technical parameters for the reference CaL-WtE plant.

Technical parameter	Unit of measurement	Value
Superheated steam temperature	°C	500
Superheated steam pressure	bar	60
Condensing type	-	cooling towers
Condensation pressure	bar	0.086
F_0/F_{CO_2}	-	0.10
F_R/F_{CO_2}	-	8
Carbonator temperature	°C	650
Carbonator CO ₂ capture efficiency	%	89.06
Carbonator SO ₂ capture efficiency	%	90.00
Stack temperature	°C	120
Calciner temperature	°C	920
Oxygen purity	%	95.00
Oxygen preheating temperature	°C	140
Oxygen concentration in oxidant gas	%	40.00
Oxygen excess at calciner outlet	% _{vol, wet basis}	3.55
Temperature of the CO ₂ recirculation	°C	400
Cyclone efficiency on Ca particles	%	99.55
Cyclone efficiency on ash particles	%	90.00
Air infiltrations in the Reactors Heat Recovery Sections	% _{wt}	1.00
Air infiltration in bag filters	% _{wt}	3.00

⁴ No major modification has been made to the Waste-to-Energy and Bio-CHP simulation models and assumptions, compared to the ones reported in D4.3 (“Base cases definition and KPIs calculation for cement, steel, Bio-CHP and WtE plants with and without capture”).

Table 13: Main technical parameters for the reference CaL-Bio-CHP plant.

Technical parameter	Unit of measurement	Value
Superheated steam temperature	°C	500
Superheated steam pressure	bar	60
Condensing type	-	cooling towers
Condensation pressure	bar	0.086
F_0/F_{CO_2}	-	0.09
F_R/F_{CO_2}	-	7
Carbonator temperature	°C	650
Carbonator CO ₂ capture efficiency	%	88.90
Carbonator SO ₂ capture efficiency	%	90.00
Stack temperature	°C	150
Calcliner temperature	°C	920
Oxygen purity	%	95.00
Oxygen preheating temperature	°C	140
Oxygen concentration in oxidant gas	%	40.00
Oxygen excess at calciner outlet	% _{vol, wet basis}	3.55
Temperature of the CO ₂ recirculation	°C	400
Cyclone efficiency on Ca particles	%	99.55
Cyclone efficiency on ash particles	%	90.00
Air infiltrations in the Reactors Heat Recovery Sections	% _{wt}	1.00
Air infiltration in bag filters	% _{wt}	3.00

3.3 CaL for steel plant

In previous D4.3, one configuration was evaluated for the application of CaL to the steel case. It corresponds to the standard CaL configuration where the solids in the loop circulate directly from reactor to reactor. The analysis included the calculation of mass and energy balances of the integrated system working under different operating conditions according to the properties of the variable flue gases produced in the Electric Arc Furnace (EAF) steelmaking plant. Furthermore, for simulating the integrated system, the CaL system was placed after the post-combustion chamber (i.e., the properties of the EAF flue gas entering the carbonator correspond to those measured at point 3 in Figure 6).

Figure 6. Schematic of the EAF plant with the location of measurement points and the points at which the CaL system was applied in D4.3 (green) and D4.4 (orange).

A set of six representative operating conditions were simulated in D4.3 to account for the variability of flue gases. Subsequently, results from these six simulations were used to interpolate and estimate average KPIs of the CO₂ capture system.

On the other hand, in the present work, several modifications were included in the methodology for the current analysis, compared to D4.3:

- The integration point of the CaL system was moved to point 1 (closer to the EAF, see Figure 3) to limit the negative impact of air infiltration on the CO₂ compositions and increase of the volumetric flow rate of flue gases.
- The simulation approach followed to include the different operating conditions (according to the EAF flue gas properties) was refined. Now, a total of 930 operating points (extracted from the measurement dataset) are simulated. Each point represents one minute of operation of the CaL system. Consequently, results from simulations are directly used to estimate the average KPIs and interpolation is not required, making the analysis more accurate. Nonetheless, the analysis carried out for this work assumed a series of quasi-steady state points and the dynamic responses of the components were not included.
- The fluidization of the carbonator is controlled by recirculating part of the CO₂-lean gas rather than by injecting supplementary air.
- The fluidization of the calciner is controlled by adjusting the CO₂-rich gas recirculation. The target is to keep the superficial gas velocity at the riser above 3 m/s.

The block diagram of the base case is presented in Figure 6, while more details are provided in subsequent paragraphs.

Figure 7: Block diagram of the base case: CaL plant without intermediate solid storage, $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ injection, or CPU vent gas recirculation.

The modelling framework was updated to include the modification described above. For the steel case, the CaL system is assumed to treat flue gases with properties measured right after the EAF (Point 1 in Figure 3). Placing the CaL system in this location would result in better performance of the capture process due to lower gas flow rates and higher CO_2 concentrations. The profiles of flue gas properties (mass flow rate, CO_2 content, and temperature) used for the analysis of this deliverable are shown in Figure 7. These profiles resulted from the processed dataset after removing unreliable values (related to issues during measurements) and lasted for 930 minutes, which a frequency of one measurement per minute. It is also important to clarify that even though only the CO_2 content profile is reported in Figure 7, simulations were performed by including CO_2 , H_2O , N_2 , and O_2 as the species in the flue gases. Other species were not included due to their low concentration and relevance to assessing the process from a systematic point of view (mass and energy balances), although the impurities may play a role in defining the deactivation and purge/make-up of the sorbent. Simulations were conducted to reproduce the mass and energy balances of the CO_2 capture plant using the profiles of EAF flue gas properties as inputs. For that, it is assumed that each of the 930 operating points represents a quasi-steady state of the operational point of the system (i.e., no dynamics effects are considered in this analysis).

The flue gases from the EAF have highly fluctuating properties and cyclic behavior. They first increase from minimum values to a peak; then, they decrease again to minimum values in periods ranging from 40 to 57 minutes. The average CO_2 flow from the EAF was calculated as 11.52 t/h.

Since the EAF flue gases to be treated exhibit high variability, a set of strategies are introduced in the CaL plant to improve its technical performance, while making the operation of some process sections less affected by the flue gas fluctuations (i.e., more stable) or even at a fixed steady state (as is the case of the CPU). Such strategies are described in Table 14.

Figure 8: Profiles of a) EAF wet flue gases' CO₂ content, b) EAF flue gases mass flow rate, and c) EAF flue gases' temperature.

Even though the EAF flue gases exhibit significant variability, the different components of the CaL plant are designed based on the most critical conditions, representing their maximum load (e.g., maximum flow rate, maximum CO₂ concentration, etc.). This allows the plant to achieve the targeted actual CO₂ capture efficiencies from the EAF process flue gases higher than 90%.

The EAF flue gases cooler located upstream of the CaL carbonator is designed to cool 81.7 kg/s of EAF flue gas from 930°C to 400°C, translating into a thermal load of 51 MW. Molten salts are used as the cooling fluid, entering the cooler at 265 °C and exiting at 540 °C.

A superficial gas velocity range of 3-7 m/s is established for the carbonator design, consistent with typical conditions for CFB systems (Ylätaalo et al., 2014). The riser cross-section area is sized based on the maximum gas volumetric flow rate of 224 m³/s at 620 °C and the highest gas velocity of 7 m/s. For conditions with lower volumetric flow rates, carbonator flue gas recirculation is employed to maintain the minimum gas velocity of 3 m/s. Although gas recirculation helped sustain the fluidisation regime in the carbonator riser, it also resulted in CO₂ dilution. The carbonator convective pass is designed using Thermoflex. The gas flow to be cooled at the design point (from 620 °C to around 280 °C) is within 87-89 kg/s for the different cases. Like in the EAF flue gas cooler, molten salts are used as the cooling fluid, entering at 265 °C and exiting at 540 °C. The calciner is designed following a similar approach and the superficial gas velocity is controlled with the recirculation of CO₂-rich gas in the range 3 – 7 m/s. For both reactors (carbonator and calciner), the height is consistent across all the cases, 20 m. This height is defined to provide sufficient residence time to the gas-solid reacting system to advance the carbonation and calcination reactions taking place in the carbonator and calciner, respectively.

The convective pass to recover heat from the gases produced in the carbonator and the calciner are designed based on the corresponding maximum mass flow rate. The temperature of gases entering the convective passes are 620°C for the carbonator and 920°C for the calciner, respectively. Moreover, they remain constant across all the simulated points since it is assumed that the average temperature of the reactors is invariant.

The external Fluidized Bed Heat Exchanger (FBHE) used to regulate the temperature of the solids entering the carbonator is designed by calculating the heat transfer area of tubes required to transfer heat from the solid bed to the molten salts flowing inside the pipes. The heat transfer calculation followed the approach and recommendation reported in (Stenberg et al., 2020)

Table 14: Description of strategies introduced to the CaL capture plant.

Feature	Description
<p>1. CO₂-lean gas recirculation</p>	<p>During periods with low EAF flue gas flow rate, a portion of CO₂-lean gases exiting the carbonator's convective pass is recirculated back to the carbonator's riser to sustain a minimum superficial gas velocity of 3 m/s in order to keep the fast fluidization regime in the reactor.</p>
<p>2. Adiabatic carbonator + external fluidized bed heat exchanger (FBHE)</p>	<p>As a result of the variable EAF flue gases, the carbonator operates under variable conditions, with fluctuations in both the solids' flow rate and the heat generated by the carbonation, driven by changes in the EAF flue gas properties. Due to this, it is defined that the carbonator temperature is controlled by an external fluidized bed heat exchanger (FBHE). This means that an adiabatic carbonator without internal heat transfer surfaces is considered in this work. The motivation for this configuration is to separate the heat extraction from the reacting-capture process, which has been reported to improve flexibility and control (Astolfi et al., 2019; Criado et al., 2017). The solids' temperature at the inlet of the carbonator is adjusted to have an average carbonator temperature of 620°C, according to the solids and CO₂ flow rates entering the reactor. The bypass level of solids through the FBHE is regulated to control the incoming solids' temperature.</p>
<p>3. Gas storage for oxygen from ASU and CO₂-rich gas to CPU</p>	<p>A cryogenic tank is placed between the calciner and the ASU to store the oxygen (-182°C, 1.2 bar) produced by the ASU. Similarly, a gas holder is located between the calciner and the CPU to store the CO₂-rich gas produced in the calciner. These strategies enable the ASU and CPU to work at a constant average load since they are decoupled from the CaL process variability.</p>
<p>4. Thermal energy storage (TES) between the CaL section and the power block</p>	<p>Since the heat sources in the CaL plant follow the fluctuations introduced by the variable EAF flue gases, the thermal power available to be recovered and subsequently used to produce electric power via a steam cycle varies rapidly and significantly and this would not be compatible with the typically limited load rate variations allowed for the massive steam cycle components. Therefore, a thermal energy storage (TES) system is employed to decouple steam cycle operation from the fluctuation in the heat sources. In the TES system, solar salt (60%_{wt} NaNO₃ - 40%_{wt} KNO₃) is stored in two tanks (hot and cold). Cold molten salt at 265°C is directed at the various heat recovery points at variable flow rates, depending on the available heat, and the resulting hot molten (540°C) salt is stored in the hot tank. This configuration provides a stable thermal input to the steam cycle.</p>

See Figure 19

Finally, the TES tanks and the steam cycle were designed using the Thermoflex package.

Once the geometries/sizes of every component were obtained, simulations were conducted to reproduce the mass and energy balance of the CaL plant. For that, the properties of the EAF flue gases (Figure 7) were used as inputs. Minute-based average values are calculated for the key EAF flue gas properties, including mass flow rate, composition (CO_2 , H_2O , O_2 , N_2), and temperature, resulting in a dataset of 930 points. Each point reflects a distinct operating condition for the CaL plant. Thus, the same number of simulations were conducted for each case by assuming a sequence of quasi-steady states (i.e., the system's dynamic response is not included in the analysis). Besides, a set of assumptions are made to reduce the complexity of simulations while maintaining a sufficient accuracy level:

- The relative CO_2 capture efficiency in the carbonator is 95% for each simulated point. The relative CO_2 capture efficiency is computed as the ratio between the actual CO_2 capture efficiency and the maximum CO_2 capture efficiency limited by equilibrium. This means that the CO_2 captured in the carbonator is 95% of the maximum possible CO_2 , that could be captured if the CO_2 equilibrium is reached. In addition, complete conversion of CaCO_3 to CaO and CO_2 is assumed in the calciner.
- Models of CaL reactors consider a single representative temperature, set as the average within each reactor under specified boundary conditions for each simulated point.

Simulations and analyses are conducted by integrating several tools, such as Aspen Plus (CaL and CPU), Matlab, Thermoflex (heat recovery and steam cycle) and Excel (result processing and TEA).

Given the local availability of waste biomass from the forest industry in the area where the EAF plant is located (North Europe), residual forestry biomass is used as the fuel for the calciner, whose properties are included in Table 15. Moreover, using residual forestry biomass as the fuel for the calciner could lead to negative emissions from the process since the CO_2 from biomass combustion can be considered biogenic and its release would not alter the atmospheric CO_2 content, while its capture and storage would be equivalent to removing CO_2 from the atmospheric air (Scope 1 emissions only considered).

Table 15: Properties of residual forestry biomass used as fuel in the calciner in the CaL plant applied to the EAF plant (Saeed et al., 2023)

Proximate analysis	Unit of measurement	Value
Volatile matter	%wt. dry basis	74.10
Fixed carbon	%wt. dry basis	21.85
Ash	%wt. dry basis	4.05
Ultimate analysis		
C - Carbon	%wt. dry basis	51.00
H - Hydrogen	%wt. dry basis	5.80
N - Nitrogen	%wt. dry basis	0.90
O - Oxygen	%wt. dry basis	38.21
S - Sulphur	%wt. dry basis	0.04
Ash	%wt. dry basis	4.05
Moisture ^(a)	%wt. wet basis	10.00
LHV	MJ/kg _{wet basis}	17.74

^(a) The 10% moisture content is assumed considering the waste biomass comes from the milling process (Gayan et al., 2004).

4 INTEGRATION OF THE IMPROVED CALCIUM LOOPING SYSTEM

4.1 Heat & material balances, integrated system and technical KPIs

This section describes which improvement options have been implemented in all the different applications and presents the estimations of their energy and environmental performance (reported in Table 16).

4.1.1 CaL for cement plants

Comparing to the previous base case of D4.3, the simulation results reported in Table 16 show minor differences in the specific fuel consumption of the calciner and rotary kiln and a corresponding increase in both the gas flow rate (generated by the kiln and the oxyfuel calciner) and solid flow rates circulating between the CaL reactors (De Lena et al., 2022). This updated simulation is based on the same configuration proposed in the previous D4.3, but with the updated model described in 3.1.

Several advanced design options have been evaluated to improve the state-of-the-art CaL-CFB cement plant in terms of CO₂ capture rate, energy efficiency, and cost of CO₂ avoided. Starting from the base CaL-CFB model, each improvement alternative has been implemented and investigated independently, without considering possible combinations of the design options. Below, each case is described and the main results are compared with those of the base case.

- **Case CPUr - CPU vent gas recirculation:** In the cement plant integrated with the CaL-CFB system with CPU, two streams are responsible for direct CO₂ emissions: (i) the kiln flue gas treated by the carbonator and (ii) the CPU vent gas. As shown in Table 16, the latter accounts for 78.5% of the total direct CO₂ emissions, emphasizing the need to handle this flow's contribution to increase the CO₂ capture rate. Thus, a straightforward solution to decarbonize this stream is to recirculate the CPU vent gas to the carbonator inlet (Figure 8). The carbonator model assumption of constant $F_R/F_0=3$ leads to a rise in the circulating sorbent flow rate due to the carbonator's higher CO₂ inlet flow rate. The larger amount of solids circulating between the CaL reactors causes higher fuel and oxygen demand in the calciner (+10.1%) and an increase in ASU and CPU electrical consumptions (+9.8%). However, due to the larger thermal power available in the carbonator and in the CO₂-rich gases directed at the CPU, the higher HRSC net electricity production (+18.4%) offset the latter. Thus, the overall CO₂ capture and avoidance rates increase by 4.6 and 6.1 percentage points, respectively, but the equivalent primary energy consumption and SPECCA increase by 0.36 MJ_{LHV}/kg_{clik} and 0.22 MJ_{LHV}/kg_{CO₂}, respectively, compared to the baseline CaL-CFB configuration.

Cement plant with integrated CaL-CFB

Figure 9: Simplified process flow diagram of the advanced case CFB-CaL cement plant with CPU vent gas recirculation.

- Case TC600 and TC550 - Reduction of carbonator temperature:** The chemical equilibrium of the exothermic carbonation reaction promotes lower CO₂ concentrations in the gas phase at lower temperatures. Hence, lower carbonator temperatures allow higher theoretical CO₂ capture efficiency. On the other hand, the major drawback of this temperature reduction lies in the slower reaction kinetics, requiring longer reactor residence time (i.e., height) to approach equilibrium. For this advanced case, the analysis has been carried out considering two values of carbonator temperature: 600°C (TC600) and 550°C (TC550), which lead to a carbonator CO₂ capture efficiency of 93.5% and 95.0%, respectively. Compared to the state-of-the-art CFB-CaL, both cases exhibit higher calciner fuel and oxygen consumption, i.e., +2.1% and +3.7%, due to the larger quantity of lower temperature sorbent from the carbonator. The higher ASU electricity consumption is offset by the increase in HRSC production driven by the larger thermal power rejected by the low-temperature carbonator. The overall direct CO₂ emissions decrease by 6.4% and 8.7%, respectively in TC600 and TC550, raising the equivalent CO₂ avoidance rate by 0.6 and 0.9 percentage points compared to the base case. However, the simulation results

also show higher equivalent primary energy consumption (+0.9% and +1.6%) and SPECCA (+0.06 and +0.10 MJ_{LHV}/kg_{CO2}) compared to the state-of-the-art configuration.

- Case HXS - Sorbent heat recovery:** One solution to reduce the calciner fuel and oxygen consumption is to raise the temperature of the sorbent delivered to the calciner. For this purpose, it is possible to transfer heat from the calciner loop seal to the carbonator loop seal via a diathermic fluid, as illustrated in Figure 9. The solids at the calciner exit release heat, preheating the sorbent from the carbonator, assuming that it is possible to reach a temperature difference of 100°C between the two flows. Compared to the base scheme, this solution reduces calciner direct fuel and oxygen consumption (-1.7%). As a consequence, the thermal power recovered in the bottom steam cycle is reduced, leading to an increase in electric power and indirect fuel consumption (+1.4%). However, this effect is well mitigated in the lower direct fuel consumption, which leads to a reduction in the equivalent primary energy consumption (-0.7%) and in the value of SPECCA (decreased by 0.06 MJ_{LHV}/kg_{CO2}).

Figure 10: Simplified process flow diagram of the CaL-CFB plant section with sorbent heat recovery between calciner and carbonator.

- Case Ca(OH)₂ - Ca(OH)₂ injection:** Thanks to the injection of a polishing stream of hydrated lime downstream of the carbonator cyclone, it is possible to reduce the direct CO₂ emission from kiln flue gases significantly. Calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)₂) is more porous and reactive than CaO-based sorbent and can react at a lower temperature with the flue gas (550°C) and achieve a CO₂ concentration close to the equilibrium value without the same kinetic limitations of the sorbent in the calciner. As shown in Figure 10, it is assumed that calcium hydroxide is produced by exploiting a portion of the sorbent purged from the CaL system, in order to minimize the overall equivalent energy consumption and CO₂ emissions (i.e. compared to an hypothetical case with an external production of calcium hydroxide). The purge is milled down to 20 μm, hydrated and then injected downstream the carbonator, with a Ca(OH)₂/CO₂ molar ratio equal to 3 (Secomandi et al., 2024). The simulation results show a reduction in the total direct CO₂ emissions at the stack compared to the base CaL-CFB of 19 percentage points, at the expense of higher fuel and oxygen consumption of the calciner (+3.1%). Indeed, the calcium hydroxide stream is generated from the calcination of fresh limestone, which is an energy-intensive process. Compared to the base case, both CO₂ capture and avoidance rates increase by 1.3 percentage points, but the equivalent primary energy consumption and SPECCA also grow by 0.17 MJ_{LHV}/kg_{clk} and 0.17 MJ_{LHV}/kg_{CO2}, respectively.

Figure 11: Simplified process flow diagram of the CaL-CFB plant section with $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ injection downstream the carbonator cyclone.

- Case O_2 electrolysis - Oxygen as by-product from electrolysis:** It is a future prospective scenario in which it is assumed that the oxygen requirement of the calciner is made available as a by-product by a nearby water electrolysis plant for hydrogen production. Thus, it is possible to avoid installing the ASU system at the cement plant and reduce the electricity consumption of the CO_2 capture section by one-third (see Table 16). Consequently, compared to the Base case scenario, the simulation indicates a reduction of 39.6% of the indirect fuel consumption and CO_2 emissions, leading to a decrease of the SPECCA index by $0.85 \text{ MJ}_{\text{LHV}}/\text{kg}_{\text{CO}_2}$.

Table 16: Heat & mass balance and CO₂ emissions KPIs of the advanced cases for cement application.

Heat & mass balance and KPIs	Unit of measurement	Base case	CPUr	TC600	TC550	HXS	Ca(OH) ₂	O ₂ electrolysis
Clinker production	tpd	2824	2827	2824	2825	2824	2835	2824
Total direct fuel consumption (q _{dir,clk})	MW _{LHV} - MJ _{LHV} /kg _{clk}	168.0 - 5.14	181.1 - 5.53	170.6 - 5.22	172.8 - 5.28	165.7 - 5.07	171.7 - 5.25	168.0 - 5.14
Fuel consumption in rotary kiln	MW _{LHV} - MJ _{LHV} /kg _{clk}	41.2 - 1.26	41.3 - 1.26	41.2 - 1.26	41.3 - 1.26	41.2 - 1.26	41.2 - 1.26	41.2 - 1.26
Fuel consumption in CaL calciner	MW _{LHV} - MJ _{LHV} /kg _{clk}	126.8 - 3.88	139.8 - 4.27	129.4 - 3.96	131.5 - 4.02	124.5 - 3.81	130.5 - 4.00	126.8 - 3.88
Oxygen input	tpd - kg _{O2} /kg _{clk}	965.4 - 0.34	1064.9 - 0.38	985.4 - 0.35	1000.3 - 0.35	949.1 - 0.34	995.3 - 0.35	965.4 - 0.34
Additional electricity consumption for CO ₂ capture	MW _e - kWh _e /t _{clk}	13.34 - 113.3	12.67 - 107.5	13.00 - 110.5	12.70 - 107.9	13.70 - 116.4	14.06 - 119.5	3.31 - 28.2
Net electricity production in steam cycle	MW _e - kWh _e /t _{clk}	17.57 - 149.3	20.82 - 176.8	18.35 - 155.9	18.94 - 160.9	16.94 - 143.9	17.38 - 147.7	17.57 - 149.3
ASU consumption	MW _e - kWh _e /t _{clk}	10.02 - 85.2	11.06 - 93.9	10.23 - 87.0	10.39 - 88.2	9.86 - 83.8	10.34 - 87.8	0.00 - 0.0
Fans consumption in CaL system	MW _e - kWh _e /t _{clk}	1.31 - 11.2	1.39 - 11.8	1.33 - 11.3	1.34 - 11.4	1.31 - 11.1	1.34 - 11.4	1.31 - 11.2
CO ₂ compression consumption	MW _e - kWh _e /t _{clk}	15.45 - 131.3	16.97 - 144.1	15.66 - 133.1	15.79 - 134.1	15.36 - 130.5	15.86 - 134.8	15.45 - 131.3
Auxiliaries (grinding processes, etc.)	MW _e - kWh _e /t _{clk}	4.12 - 35.0	4.07 - 34.6	4.12 - 35.0	4.12 - 35.0	4.12 - 35.0	3.91 - 33.3	4.12 - 35.0
CO₂ emissions and KPIs								
CO ₂ captured in carbonator	%	90.0	90.0	93.5	95.0	90.0	90.0	90.0
CO ₂ avoided from flue gases	%	91.2	97.4	91.7	91.9	91.3	92.8	91.2
Overall CO ₂ capture ratio	%	93.6	98.2	94.0	94.2	93.6	94.9	93.6
Total direct CO ₂ emissions at stack (e _{dir,CO2})	kg _{CO2} /s - kg _{CO2} /t _{clk}	2.5 - 76.4	0.7 - 22.8	2.3 - 71.5	2.3 - 69.8	2.4 - 75.4	2.0 - 61.9	2.5 - 76.4
Direct CO ₂ emissions from kiln flue gases	kg _{CO2} /s - kg _{CO2} /t _{clk}	0.5 - 16.4	0.7 - 22.8	0.3 - 10.4	0.3 - 8.0	0.5 - 16.0	0.0 - 0.0	0.5 - 16.4
Direct CO ₂ emissions from CPU vent gas	kg _{CO2} /s - kg _{CO2} /t _{clk}	2.0 - 60.0	0.0 - 0.0	2.0 - 61.1	2.0 - 61.8	1.9 - 59.4	2.0 - 61.9	2.0 - 60.0
Indirect CO ₂ emission (e _{indir,CO2})	kg _{CO2} /s - kg _{CO2} /t _{clk}	1.9 - 57.1	1.8 - 55.7	1.8 - 56.3	1.8 - 55.7	1.9 - 57.9	1.9 - 59.2	1.1 - 34.5
Equivalent CO ₂ emissions (e _{eq,CO2})	kg _{CO2} /s - kg _{CO2} /t _{clk}	4.4 - 133.5	2.6 - 78.5	4.2 - 127.9	4.1 - 125.4	4.4 - 133.4	4.0 - 121.1	3.6 - 111.0
Equivalent CO ₂ avoidance rate	%	85.2	91.3	85.8	86.1	85.2	86.5	87.7
Indirect primary energy consumption	MW _{LHV} - MJ _{LHV} /kg _{clk}	49.4 - 1.51	48.3 - 1.48	48.8 - 1.49	48.2 - 1.47	50.1 - 1.53	51.2 - 1.57	29.9 - 0.91
Equivalent primary energy consumption	MW _{LHV} - MJ _{LHV} /kg _{clk}	217.4 - 6.65	229.4 - 7.01	219.4 - 6.71	220.9 - 6.76	215.8 - 6.60	222.9 - 6.82	197.8 - 6.05
SPECCA	MJ _{LHV} /kg _{CO2}	3.24	3.46	3.30	3.35	3.18	3.41	2.39

4.1.2 CaL for waste to energy and bio-CHP plants

Various configurations of the WtE-CaL plant have been simulated by adding some process improvement options, summarized in the assumptions of Table 17. The aim is to identify the optimal designs that enhance CO₂ capture rates, improve energy efficiency, and reduce the cost of CO₂ avoided. Below, each case is described, and the main results are compared (see Table 18, Table 19, and Table 20). The case CPU_r is considered as the reference case, as all the other modified configurations are featured by CPU vent gas recirculation plus other process improvement options.

Figure 16 shows the detailed thermal balance of the cases.

Table 17: Assumptions of the simulated cases for the CaL-WtE plant.

	Base case	CPU _r (reference case)	CPU _r Ca(OH) ₂ opt 1	CPU _r Ca(OH) ₂ opt 2	CPU _r TC 550	CPU _r HXS	CPU _r TC 550 HXS	Combined
CPU vent gas recirculation	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
T carbonator (°C)	650	650	650	650	550	650	550	600
Solid regenerative pre-heating	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Ca(OH) ₂ injection	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
F ₀ /F _{CO₂}	0.10	0.10	0.35	0.35	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.25

- Case CPU_r - CPU vent gas recirculation:** A straightforward solution to maximize CO₂ capture efficiency is to recycle the vent gas of the CPU back to the carbonator (see Figure 11). This approach results in a significantly higher global CCR than the base case, achieving 94.5% versus 85.8%. In this configuration, the gas entering the carbonator contains higher CO₂ concentrations than in the Base case, improving the carbon capture efficiency by 1.3 percentage points. Furthermore, due to the higher CO₂ inflow to the carbonator and the constant parameter F_R/F_{CO₂}, the flow rate of the circulating sorbent rises. This results in greater consumption of fuel and oxygen in the calciner (increased by 22%), higher electricity production and higher consumption by the CPU, ASU and auxiliaries. However, the net electrical efficiency of the steam cycle is the same and consequently also the SPECCA is unvaried with respect to the base case.

Figure 12: Simplified process flow diagram of the CaL system for the WtE plant with CPU vent gas recirculation (Case CPUr).

- Case CPUr $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ opt 1 - CPU vent gas recirculation + $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ injection option 1:** This case, in addition to the modifications presented in the reference case, i.e. the case CPUr, considers the injection of a polishing stream of hydrated lime into a duct located downstream of the carbonator after the flue gas has been cooled to 550°C (see Figure 12). This modification was implemented because $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ reacts with flue gas at a lower temperature, enabling it to achieve a CO_2 concentration close to the equilibrium value without experiencing the same kinetic limitations as the sorbent in the carbonator and a significant reduction in direct CO_2 emissions at the stack (-99.8%). Similar to $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ case developed for the cement application, calcium hydroxide is produced using the CaL-purge stream, which is hydrated and injected downstream of the carbonator with a $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2/\text{CO}_2$ molar ratio of 3. The ratio F_0/F_{CO_2} is increased to 0.35 in order to have enough purge to produce the necessary $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$. This leads to a significant increase in the calciner fuel consumption ($+55.9\%$, compared to base case). Moreover, as clearly visible in Figure 16, the fraction of thermal power necessary for the first calcination of this material is much higher compared to the case CPUr (12.1% vs 4.2%), while the fraction converted into electric power (i.e. the net electric efficiency) decreases. Finally, it is worth noting that the CCR approaches nearly 100% , and the SPECCA index shows an increase of 66.7% compared to the base case.

Figure 13: Simplified process flow diagram of the CaL system for the WtE plant with CPU vent gas recirculation and Ca(OH)₂ injection downstream the carbonator cyclone (Case CPUr Ca(OH)₂ opt 1).

- Case CPUr Ca(OH)₂ opt 2 - CPU vent gas recirculation + Ca(OH)₂ injection option 2:** This case builds on the modifications presented in the reference case and introduces the direct injection of Ca(OH)₂ into the upper section of the carbonator, which is cooled to 550°C, while the lower section remains at 650°C (see Figure 13). Thanks to the lower temperature and to the Ca(OH)₂ injection, the carbonator capture efficiency is much higher than the baseline case, with an increase of 11.9 percentage points. This leads to a significantly higher global CCR, increasing from 85.8% to 99.8%. It also substantially reduces direct CO₂ emissions at the stack, decreasing by 98.2%. As observed in the previous case, the simulation results indicate an increase in the calciner fuel and oxygen by 83.3%, respectively, in addition to a rise in the SPECCA index of 47.9% compared to the baseline case.

Figure 14: Simplified process flow diagram of the CaL system for the WtE plant with CPU vent gas recirculation and Ca(OH)₂ injection in the upper section of the carbonator (Case CPUr Ca(OH)₂ opt 2).

- Case CPUr TC 550 - CPU vent gas recirculation + carbonator temperature reduction:** Case CPUr TC 550 operates under the same assumptions as reference case, except the carbonator's operating temperature, which is set at 550°C. This adjustment alters the equilibrium conditions, resulting in a lower CO₂ concentration at the carbonator outlet, a higher carbonator capture efficiency, and an increased global CCR of 97.5% compared to 94.5% in the reference case. In comparison to the baseline case and reference case, this configuration shows (i) a significantly higher calciner fuel and oxygen consumption due to lower temperature of the sorbent at the exit of the carbonator; (ii) an increase in electricity consumption by the CPU and ASU; (iii) a rise in net electricity production; (iv) a reduction of the SPECCA index from 4.0 MJ_{LHV}/kg_{CO₂} to 3.8 MJ_{LHV}/kg_{CO₂}.
- Case CPUr HXS - CPU vent gas recirculation + sorbent heat recovery:** Case CPUr HXS maintains the same assumptions as reference case but introduces a regenerative heat exchange between the sorbent leaving the carbonator and the sorbent coming from the calciner (see Figure 14). It is assumed that a heat transfer fluid circulating within the walls of the loop seals cools the solids exiting the calciner while heating the solids leaving the carbonator. This regeneration allows a significant reduction of fuel consumption with respect to the reference case (-13.6%). Nevertheless, the net electric efficiency of the steam cycle slightly decreases, which leads to a small increase of the SPECCA index, from 4.0 to 4.1.

Figure 15: Simplified process flow diagram of the CaL system for the WtE plant with CPU vent gas recirculation and sorbent heat recovery between calciner and carbonator (Case CPUr HXS).

- Case CPUr TC 550 HXS - CPU vent gas recirculation + sorbent heat recovery + carbonator temperature reduction:** Case CPUr TC 550 HXS shares the same assumptions as Case CPUr HXS, except for the carbonator's operating temperature, which is set at 550°C. The combined effect of recirculating the CPU vent gas, preheating the sorbent, and lowering the carbonator temperature results in energy-related KPIs similar to those of the reference case: RDF and oxygen consumption are slightly lower (-2%), while the net electric efficiency decreases by a half percentage point. The lower temperature of the carbonator allows to achieve a high carbonator's capture efficiency and global CCR (which are almost identical to those of case CPUr TC 550), while the regenerative solid heat exchanger helps to reduce fuel consumption. Consequently, the SPECCA index is lower than the reference case, thanks to the higher CCR, but slightly higher than case CPUr TC 550, due to the lower RDF consumption and electrical energy production.
- Case Combined - CPU vent gas recirculation + Ca(OH)₂ injection + sorbent heat recovery + carbonator temperature reduction:** Case Combined combines all the previous configuration. CPU vent gas is recirculated, Ca(OH)₂ is injected downstream of the carbonator (as in case CPUr Ca(OH)₂ opt 1), the operating temperature of the carbonator is lowered (600°C), and the sorbent delivered to the calciner is preheated by cooling down the sorbent going to the carbonator (see Figure 15). As in case CPUr Ca(OH)₂ opt 1 and CPUr Ca(OH)₂ opt 2, the ratio F_0/F_{CO_2} is increased in order to produce the necessary Ca(OH)₂. The calcination of this additional make-up, together with the lower temperature of the carbonator, leads to a higher RDF consumption, while the beneficial contribution of the regenerative solid heat exchanger allows to reduce it. As a result, the fuel consumption increases by 5.8% with respect to the reference case. On the other hand, the lower operating temperature in the carbonator, combined with the effects of Ca(OH)₂ injection, results in several benefits: with

respect to the reference case, this case features a higher carbonator capture efficiency (+3.6 percentage points), an increase in the global CCR (+5.3 percentage points), and a significant reduction of direct CO₂ avoided (+4.3 percentage points). However, looking at the SPECCA index (which is much higher than Case 1, 5.7 MJ_{LHV}/kg_{CO2} vs 4.0 MJ_{LHV}/kg_{CO2}), it emerges that the energy penalty of the in-situ Ca(OH)₂ production, overcomes the energy saving due to the regenerative solid pre-heating, and also the higher CCR achieved.

Figure 16: Simplified process flow diagram of the CaL system for the WtE plant with CPU vent gas recirculation, sorbent heat recovery between calciner and carbonator and Ca(OH)₂ injection downstream the carbonator cyclone (Case Combined).

Table 18: Main results of the mass and energy balance of the CaL-WtE plant.

	Unit of measurement	Base case	CPUr (reference case)	CPUr Ca(OH) ₂ opt 1	CPUr Ca(OH) ₂ opt 2	CPUr TC 550	CPUr HXS	CPUr TC 550 HXS	Combined
RDF (calcliner fuel) mass flow	t/h	48.22	58.84	75.07	88.64	72.23	50.86	57.69	62.28
RDF power input	MW _{LHV}	222.33	271.33	346.16	408.72	333.05	234.53	266.02	287.20
Oxygen mass flow	t/h	73.74	90.01	114.94	135.16	110.08	78.13	88.45	95.69
Make-up mass flow	t/h	19.02	23.04	84.72	87.08	23.77	22.65	23.06	58.69
X _{CO₂,in,Carb}	% _{vol}	9.52	10.89	11.26	11.47	11.12	10.77	10.90	11.03
Electric power balance									
Steam turbine power	MW _e	77.21	93.45	101.62	126.93	115.92	80.02	91.47	89.69
Flue gas FD fan consumption	MW _e	2.74	2.74	2.74	2.74	2.74	2.74	2.74	2.74
Flue gas ID fan	MW _e	0.93	0.86	0.89	0.90	0.86	0.86	0.85	0.87
CO ₂ recirculation fan	MW _e	1.18	1.42	1.81	2.13	1.74	1.11	1.40	1.51
BFW pump	MW _e	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.08	0.07	0.05	0.06	0.06
Cooling Tower loop pump	MW _e	0.65	0.78	0.87	1.06	0.97	0.67	0.77	0.75
Cooling Tower fans	MW _e	0.39	0.47	0.54	0.64	0.59	0.40	0.46	0.45
ASU consumption	MW _e	17.45	21.29	27.19	31.98	26.04	18.48	20.93	22.64
CPU consumption	MW _e	20.78	25.42	32.95	36.37	29.40	23.47	25.84	28.82
Net electric power output	MW _e	32.20	39.36	33.31	49.59	52.26	31.32	37.39	30.78
Steam cycle net electric efficiency	%	14.5	14.5	9.6	12.1	15.7	13.4	14.1	10.7

Table 19: CO₂ balance of the simulated cases for the CaL-WtE plant.

	Unit of measurement	Base case	CPUr (reference case)	CPUr Ca(OH) ₂ opt 1	CPUr Ca(OH) ₂ opt 2	CPUr TC 550	CPUr HXS	CPUr TC 550 HXS	Combined
CO ₂ from WtE	t/h	83.62	83.62	83.62	83.62	83.62	83.62	83.62	83.62
CO ₂ from RDF	t/h	77.35	94.39	120.47	142.19	115.86	81.59	92.55	99.91
CO ₂ from limestone calcination	t/h	8.36	10.13	37.26	38.29	10.45	9.96	10.14	25.81
Total CO₂ in	t/h	169.33	188.15	241.35	264.10	209.93	175.17	186.31	209.34
CO ₂ to storage	t/h	145.30	177.86	230.83	253.46	204.74	164.95	181.26	202.58
CO ₂ to stack	t/h	9.17	9.83	0.04	0.42	4.70	9.77	4.57	6.28
CO ₂ in CPU vent gases	t/h	14.48	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CO ₂ in bag filter solids	t/h	0.37	0.46	10.49	10.24	0.50	0.45	0.48	6.40
Total CO₂ out	t/h	169.32	188.15	241.36	264.12	209.94	175.17	186.31	215.27

Table 20: Technical KPIs of CaL applications to WtE plant.

	Unit of measurement	Base case	CPUr (reference case)	CPUr Ca(OH) ₂ opt 1	CPUr Ca(OH) ₂ opt 2	CPUr TC 550	CPUr HXS	CPUr TC 550 HXS	Combined
CaL fuel (RDF) consumption	kt/y - TJ _{LHV} /y	386 - 6403	471 - 7814	601 - 9969	709 - 11771	578 - 9592	407 - 6754	462 - 7661	498 - 8271
WtE fuel (MSW) consumption	kt/y - TJ _{LHV} /y	700 - 7000	700 - 7000	700 - 7000	700 - 7000	700 - 7000	700 - 7000	700 - 7000	700 - 7000
Overall Fuel consumption	kt/y - TJ _{LHV} /y	1086 - 13403	1171 - 14814	1301 - 16969	1409 - 18771	1278 - 16592	1107 - 13754	1162 - 14661	1198 - 15271
Net WtE electric energy production	MW _e - MWh _e /y	70 - 560	70 - 560	70 - 560	70 - 560	70 - 560	70 - 560	70 - 560	70 - 560
Net CaL electric energy production	MW _e - MWh _e /y	32.2 - 257.6	39.4 - 314.9	33.3 - 266.4	49.6 - 396.7	52.3 - 418.0	31.3 - 250.6	37.4 - 299.1	30.8 - 246.3
WtE Net efficiency	%	28.8	28.8	28.8	28.8	28.8	28.8	28.8	28.8
WtE+CaL Net efficiency	%	22.0	21.3	17.5	18.3	21.2	21.2	21.1	19.0
Carbonator CO ₂ capture efficiency	%	89.0	90.3	90.6	99.6	95.5	90.2	95.5	93.9
CO ₂ emissions from WtE	kt/y - kg/t _{MSW}	669 - 955.7	669 - 955.7	669 - 955.7	669 - 955.7	669 - 955.7	669 - 955.7	669 - 955.7	669 - 955.7
Direct CO ₂ emissions at stack	kt/y - kg/t _{MSW}	189.1 - 270.2	78.7 - 112.4	0.3 - 0.4	3.4 - 4.8	37.6 - 53.7	78.2 - 111.7	36.5 - 52.2	50.2 - 71.7
Indirect CO ₂ emissions	kt/y - kg/t _{MSW}	-311 - -444.8	-381 - -543.8	-322 - -460.1	-480 - -685.0	-505 - 721.9	-303 - -432.7	-362 - -516.6	-298 - 425.3
Equivalent CO ₂ emissions	kt/y - kg/t _{MSW}	-122 - -174.6	-302 - -431.4	-322 - -459.7	-476 - -680.2	-468 - -668.2	-225 - -321.1	-325 - -464.4	-247 - 353.5
Net CO ₂ emissions	kt/y - kg/t _{MSW}	-703 - -1004	-937 - -1338	-1005 - -1435	-1230 - -1757	-1171 - -1673	-819 - 1170	-954 - -1363	-879 - 1256
CO ₂ avoided from flue gas	%	71.7	88.2	100.0	99.5	94.4	88.3	94.5	92.5
CCR (CO ₂ Capture Rate)	%	85.8	94.5	100.0	99.8	97.5	94.2	97.3	99.8
SPECCA	MJ _{LHV} /kg _{CO2}	4.0	4.0	6.7	5.9	3.8	4.1	3.9	5.7

Figure 17: Detail of the thermal balance of CaL application to WtE plant.

Several configurations of the Bio-CHP plant have been developed using the same approach as for the WtE plant (see Table 21). The cases are as follows:

- **Case CPUr - CPU Vent Gas Recirculation:** This case maintains all the same assumptions as the base case, except that the CPU vent gas is recirculated back to the carbonator.
- **Case CPUr Ca(OH)₂ - CPU Vent Gas Recirculation + Ca(OH)₂ Injection:** This case builds on case CPUr by adding the injection of calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)₂) into a duct located downstream of the carbonator after the flue gas has been cooled to 550°C.
- **Case CPUr TC 550 - CPU Vent Gas Recirculation + Carbonator Temperature Reduction:** In this case, all assumptions from case CPUr are preserved except for the operating temperature of the carbonator, which is set at 550°C.
- **Case CPUr HXS - CPU Vent Gas Recirculation + Sorbent Heat Recovery:** This case keeps the same assumptions as case CPUr but includes the preheating of the sorbent delivered to the calciner.
- **Case CPUr TC 550 HXS - CPU Vent Gas Recirculation + Sorbent Heat Recovery + Carbonator Temperature Reduction:** This case maintains all assumptions from case CPUr HXS, with the addition of reducing the operating temperature of the carbonator to 550°C.

- Case Combined - CPU Vent Gas Recirculation + Ca(OH)₂ Injection + Sorbent Heat Recovery + Carbonator Temperature Reduction:** This case combines all the previous configuration. CPU vent gas is recirculated, Ca(OH)₂ is injected downstream of the carbonator (as in Case CPUr Ca(OH)₂), the operating temperature of the carbonator is lowered (600°C), and the sorbent delivered to the calciner is preheated by cooling down the sorbent going to the carbonator.

Each case introduces various combinations of recirculation, temperature adjustments, and Ca(OH)₂ injections to identify the optimal designs that enhance CO₂ capture rates, improve energy efficiency, and reduce the cost of CO₂ avoided of the Bio-CHP plant. The case CPUr is considered as the reference case, as all the other modified configurations are featured by CPU vent gas recirculation plus other process improvement options.

Table 21: Assumptions of the simulated cases for the Cal-Bio-CHP plant.

	Base case	CPUr (reference case)	CPUr Ca(OH) ₂	CPUr TC 550	CPUr HXS	CPUr TC 550 HXS	Combined
CPU vent gas recirculation	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
T carbonator (°C)	650	650	650	550	650	550	600
Solid regenerative pre-heating	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Ca(OH) ₂ injection	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
F ₀ /F _{CO2}	0.09	0.09	0.37	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.26

The main results for each case, summarized in Table 22, Table 23 and Table 24 follow the trend previously described for the WtE plant. This consistency is understandable, as the same plant configurations were analyzed. The main parameters that distinguish the two applications are the characteristics of the Bio-CHP plant's flue gases at the stack and the type of fuel used in the calciner (for further details, please refer to section 3.2). Since the CO₂ concentration in the flue gases is higher than that in the WtE application, a lower F_R/F_{CO2} ratio is necessary to achieve a CO₂ capture efficiency close to or exceeding 90%, resulting in reduced fuel and oxygen consumption.

Table 22: Main results of the mass and energy balance of the CaL-Bio-CHP plant.

	Unit of measurement	Base case	CPUr (reference case)	CPUr Ca(OH) ₂	CPUr TC 550	CPUr HXS	CPUr TC 550 HXS	Combined
Pellet (calcliner fuel) mass flow	t/h	16.45	19.49	25.82	23.51	16.79	19.25	21.51
Pellet power input	MW _{LHV}	84.74	100.37	132.98	121.07	86.48	99.14	110.77
Oxygen mass flow	t/h	25.69	30.44	40.36	36.57	26.36	30.14	33.74
Make-up mass flow	t/h	7.24	8.53	36.86	8.74	8.41	8.55	25.23
X _{CO₂,in,Carb}	% _{vol}	13.05	14.40	14.82	14.60	14.29	14.42	14.60
Electric power balance								
Steam turbine power	MW _e	29.85	34.99	38.39	42.40	30.03	34.57	34.51
Flue gas FD fan consumption	MW _e	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91
Flue gas ID fan	MW _e	0.28	0.26	0.27	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.26
CO ₂ recirculation fan	MW _e	0.41	0.48	0.63	0.58	0.41	0.47	0.53
BFW pump	MW _e	0.25	0.29	0.33	0.36	0.25	0.29	0.29
Cooling Tower loop pump	MW _e	0.06	0.07	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.07	0.07
Cooling Tower fans	MW _e	0.07	0.09	0.10	0.11	0.07	0.09	0.09
ASU consumption	MW _e	6.09	7.21	9.56	8.66	6.25	7.14	8.00
CPU consumption	MW _e	8.26	9.80	13.12	11.15	9.08	10.01	11.52
Net electric power output	MW _e	13.45	15.80	13.28	20.20	12.66	15.25	12.75
Steam cycle net electric efficiency	%	15.9	15.7	10.0	16.7	14.6	15.4	11.5

Table 23: CO₂ balance of the simulated cases for the CaL-Bio-CHP plant.

	Unit of measurement	Base case	CPUr (reference case)	CPUr Ca(OH) ₂	CPUr TC 550	CPUr HXS	CPUr TC 550 HXS	Combined
CO ₂ from Bio-CHP	t/h	35.37	35.37	35.37	35.37	35.37	35.37	35.37
CO ₂ from pellet in CaL calciner	t/h	29.42	34.85	46.17	42.04	30.03	34.42	38.46
CO ₂ from limestone calcination	t/h	3.18	3.75	16.21	3.84	3.70	3.76	11.09
Total CO₂ in	t/h	67.98	73.98	97.75	81.25	69.10	73.56	84.93
CO ₂ to storage	t/h	58.57	69.45	93.07	78.77	64.61	71.12	81.96
CO ₂ to stack	t/h	3.92	4.35	0.005	2.29	4.31	2.24	2.77
CO ₂ in CPU vent gases	t/h	5.33	-	-	-	-	-	-
CO ₂ in bag filter solids	t/h	0.16	0.19	4.69	0.20	0.18	0.20	2.93
Total CO₂ out	t/h	67.98	73.98	97.76	81.26	69.10	73.56	87.66

Table 24: Technical KPIs of CaL applications to Bio-CHP plant.

	Unit of measurement	Base case	CPUr (reference case)	CPUr Ca(OH) ₂	CPUr TC 550	CPUr HXS	CPUr TC 550 HXS	Combined
CaL fuel (pellet) consumption	kt/y - TJ _{LHV} /y	132 - 2441	156 - 2891	207 - 3830	188 - 3487	134 - 2491	154 - 2855	172 - 3190
Bio-CHP fuel (MSW) consumption	kt/y - TJ _{LHV} /y	210 - 3893	210 - 3893	210 - 3893	210 - 3893	210 - 3893	210 - 3893	210 - 3893
Overall Fuel consumption	kt/y - TJ _{LHV} /y	342 - 6334	366 - 6784	417 - 7723	398 - 7380	344 - 6384	364 - 6749	382 - 7083
Net Bio-CHP electric energy production	MW _e - MWh _e /y	39 - 313	39 - 313	39 - 313	39 - 313	39 - 313	39 - 313	39 - 313
Net CaL electric energy production	MW _e - MWh _e /y	13.4 - 107.6	15.8 - 126.4	13.3 - 106.2	20.2 - 161.6	12.7 - 101.3	15.2 - 122.0	12.8 - 102.0
Bio-CHP Net efficiency	%	28.9	28.9	28.9	28.9	28.9	28.9	28.9
Bio-CHP +CaL Net efficiency	%	23.9	23.3	19.5	23.1	23.4	23.2	21.1
Carbonator CO ₂ capture efficiency	%	88.9	89.6	89.7	94.6	89.5	94.6	93.5
CO ₂ emissions from Bio-CHP	kt/y - kg/t _{MSW}	283 - 1347.6	283 - 1347.6	283 - 1347.6	283 - 1347.6	283 - 1347.6	283 - 1347.6	283 - 1347.6
Direct CO ₂ emissions at stack	kt/y - kg/t _{MSW}	74.0 - 352.3	34.8 - 165.6	0.0 - 0.2	18.3 - 87.1	34.5 - 164.1	17.9 - 85.3	22.2 - 105.5
Indirect CO ₂ emissions	kt/y - kg/t _{MSW}	-129 - -615.4	-152 - -723.2	-128 - -607.6	-194 - -924.5	-122 - -579.6	-147 - -697.8	-123 - -583.5
Equivalent CO ₂ emissions	kt/y - kg/t _{MSW}	-55 - -263.1	-117 - -557.6	-128 - -607.4	-176 - -837.4	-87 - -415.5	-129 - -612.5	-100 - -478.0
Net CO ₂ emissions	kt/y - kg/t _{MSW}	-572 - -2726	-677 - -3226	-742 - -3535	-794 - -3779	-609 - -2900	-685 - -3264	-668 - -3179
CO ₂ avoided from flue gas	%	73.9	87.7	100.0	93.5	87.8	93.7	92.2
CCR (CO ₂ Capture Rate)	%	86.2	93.9	100.0	96.9	93.5	96.7	96.5
SPECCA	MJ _{LHV} /kg _{CO2}	3.3	3.3	6.1	3.2	3.3	3.2	5.0

4.1.3 CaL for steel plants

Besides the base case described in Section 3.3, three additional configurations of the CaL plant were analyzed. The goal is to assess the impact of a set of advanced strategies to enhance the performance and, where possible, increase the capture efficiency (up to 99% of the total carbon input to the process) of the CaL CO₂ capture system applied to the EAF steelmaking. The three cases analyzed are listed below and schematically represented in Figure 17:

- CaL plant with two intermediate solid storages.
- CaL plant without intermediate solid storage, including advanced capture strategies (CPU vent gas recirculation and Ca(OH)₂ injection).
- CaL plant with intermediate solid storage, including advanced capture strategies (CPU vent gas recirculation and Ca(OH)₂ injection).

Including intermediate solid storage between the CaL reactors allows reducing the impact of fluctuating flue gases in the operation of the calciner and downstream equipment (CPU and ASU). This strategy consists of putting two solid storages to receive the solids produced by the carbonator and the calciner, respectively. Thus, the variability in the composition of solids from the carbonator can be reduced since they mixed with the solid inventory in the solid storage, leading to more uniform solid compositions at the inlet of the calciner. As a result, the fuel demand and volumetric flow rate of gas in the calciner riser are more stable. A solid inventory of the intermediate solid storage of 750 tonnes is defined to limit the minimum superficial velocity in the calciner riser to 85% of the maximum value. This applies for the two cases with intermediate solid storage. Since the calciner operates with less variability, a maximum superficial gas velocity in the calciner riser is set to 5 m/s for these cases. Similarly to the base case, the CaL reactors (carbonator and calciner) have a height of 20 m across all the three additional cases.

Besides intermediate solid storage, the Ca(OH)₂ injection and CPU vent gas recirculation are also studied to improve the CO₂ capture efficiency of the CaL plant for the steel case. It is defined that the Ca(OH)₂ is produced in the plant. For that, the input of fresh limestone (make-up) is increased so that the CaO present in the purge is enough to produce the required Ca(OH)₂ in hydration unit.

The following assumptions apply to cases with intermediate solid storage and/or Ca(OH)₂ injection and CPU vent gas recirculation:

- The Ca(OH)₂ is injected downstream the carbonator cyclone, after cooling the flue gases to 550°C.
- 95% of the maximum possible CO₂, as dictated by the equilibrium of CO₂, is captured in the polishing zone, where Ca(OH)₂ is injected to have a Ca(OH)₂ to CO₂ molar ratio of 3.0 (Secomandi et al., 2024).
- Intermediate solid storage units are assumed to be fluidized beds operating at minimum fluidization (superficial gas velocity: 0.5 m/s), where incoming solids mix instantly with the solid inventory in the vessel.

The four cases considered (base + three cases described in this section) are included in Table 25, where the presence of the advanced strategies is specified. Moreover, a general schematic of the full CaL plant including all the advanced strategies is presented in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Block diagram of the different advanced plant configurations analysed in D4.4. a) CaL plant with intermediate solid storage, b) CaL plant with Ca(OH)_2 injection and CPU vent gas recirculation, and c) CaL plant with intermediate solid storage, Ca(OH)_2 injection, and CPU vent gas recirculation.

Table 25: Different plant configurations according to the presence of the different strategies implemented.

Simulated case	Features in Table 14	Intermediate solid storage	CPU vent-gas recirculation	Ca(OH) ₂ injection
No storage - standard (NST-std)	Yes	No	No	No
No storage - advanced (NST-adv)	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Two storage - standard (2ST-std)	Yes	Yes	No	No
Two storage - advanced (2ST-adv)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Figure 19: CaL plant application to EAF steelmaking simplified process flow diagram.

The average technical KPIs for each analyzed case are reported in Table 26. The advanced cases resulted in higher average fuel consumption in the calciner due to the increased flow rate of fresh limestone that should be calcined to produce the Ca(OH)₂ injected in the polishing zone. Furthermore, implementing Ca(OH)₂ injection and CPU vent gas recirculation resulted in CO₂ capture rates higher than 99%, which significantly improved compared to the standard cases (~91%). Consequently, the direct CO₂ emissions for the advanced case are in the order of 0.1 t/h. Additionally,

despite the fuel consumption increment, the specific fuel consumption decreased. This is explained by the fact that the additional fuel consumption led to a proportional increase in the CO₂ capture from the limestone calcination plus the extra CO₂ captured with the Ca(OH)₂ produced from the calcined limestone. Finally, higher biomass fuel consumption in advanced cases also results in more CO₂ being removed from the atmosphere (hence, the net emissions are more negative).

Table 26: Average results of the mass and energy balance of the CaL-EAF plant.

	Unit of measurement	NST-STD	2ST-STD	NST-ADV	2ST-ADV
Calciner biomass consumption	t/h	9.4	8.9	11.7	11.1
Calciner fuel chemical power input	MW _{LHV}	46.2	43.7	57.9	54.9
Oxygen consumption	t/h	13.8	13.1	17.4	16.5
Limestone Make-up consumption	t/h	3.1	3.3	13.0	13.1
Ca(OH) ₂ injected into polishing zone	t/h	-	-	7.9	7.8
CO ₂ from EAF off-gases	t/h - %	11.5 - 40.2	11.5 - 41.3	11.5 - 31.1	11.5 - 32.0
CO ₂ from fuel	t/h - %	15.8 - 55.1	14.9 - 53.5	19.8 - 53.4	18.7 - 52.0
CO ₂ from make-up	t/h - %	1.4 - 4.7	1.4 - 5.2	5.7 - 15.4	5.8 - 16.0
Total CO ₂ entering the CaL plant	t/h	28.7	27.8	37.0	36.0
CO ₂ in solids recovered in carbonator fabric filter	t/h	0.05	0.05	1.41	1.39
CO ₂ loss in CO ₂ -lean gas	t/h	1.01	1.01	0.14	0.13
CO ₂ to storage from CPU	t/h	26.0	25.5	35.45	34.48
CO ₂ released in CPU vent gas	t/h	1.64	1.4	0.00	0.00
Carbonator capture efficiency ^(a)	%	91.3 (87.3)	91.3 (87.4)	98.9 (88.3)	98.5 (88.2)
Capture efficiency CaL plant	%	90.8	91.9	99.6	99.6
Direct CO ₂ emissions ^(b)	t/h	2.65	2.41	0.14	0.13
Specific fuel consumption ^(c)	MJ/kg _{CO2}	6.0 (15.8)	6.2 (15.0)	5.4 (15.8)	5.3 (15.2)
Atmospheric net CO ₂ balance ^(d)	t/h	-13.4	-12.6	-19.6	-18.6
Volume of gas holder for CO ₂ -rich gas storing	m ³	54300	14596	55940	12268
CaL plant power balance					
Steam cycle net output	MW _e	16.69	16.27	17.97	16.62
CaL section power consumption	MW _e	-2.82	-3.93	-2.89	-3.97
CPU power consumption	MW _e	-3.70	-3.60	-4.99	-4.84
ASU power consumption	MW _e	-8.83	-8.35	-11.08	-10.52
CaL plant net power^(e)	MW_e	1.34	0.39	-0.99	-2.56

^(a) Values inside brackets correspond to the CO₂ capture efficiency in carbonator's riser (i.e., without considering the recirculation of CO₂-lean gas.

^(b) It is the sum of CO₂ released to the atmosphere in the CO₂-lean gas at the carbonator's stack and the CPU vent-gas.

^(c) Values inside brackets correspond to the fuel consumption to capture 1 kg of CO₂ from the EAF flue gases only.

^(d) Since the CO₂ in the calciner fuel (residual forestry biomass) is assumed to be biogenic, CO₂ is removed from the atmosphere. This result was obtained without considering impacts from biomass pre-processing and transportation or changes in land use.

^(e) A positive value refers to the electric power available to be exported from the CaL plant. Conversely, a negative value refers to the electric power that should be imported to cover the auxiliaries power consumption.

Regarding the electric power balance of the plants, the ASU consumes between 51% and 63% of the net power produced by the steam cycle due to the high electricity demand of the ASU to produce liquid oxygen (purity of 95

vol%) of 638 kWh/t_{CO2} (Šulc and Ditzl, 2021). Besides, introducing intermediate solid storages increased the CaL section power consumption by about 38% due to the power needed to fluidize the solid storages. The plant is nearly self-sustaining from an electricity standpoint, as the net power produced by the steam cycle is very close to the total auxiliary electric power required by the capture unit (i.e., the sum of the ASU, compressors, fan, pumps, cooling tower, etc.), so the net electricity import for the CO₂ capture section is close to zero (although the steel plant still maintain the original electricity input needed to operate the EAF).

4.2 Economic analysis

The methodology followed for the economic analysis is in line with the CEMCAP framework (CEMCAP, 2018b) with some updates on the electricity and fuel costs and on the CO₂ tax price. The assumptions are listed in Table 27. More detailed information about the methodology are reported in D4.3.

Table 27: Main assumptions for economic analysis.

Economic parameter	Unit of measurement	Value
Reference year of the investment cost estimation	-	2023
Plant operational life	years	25
Debt ratio	-	50%
Nominal return on debt	-	8%
Equity ratio	-	50%
Nominal return on equity	-	8%
Inflation adjusted discount rate	-	5%
Number of additional workers required	-	20
Worker unitary cost	€/y	60000
Tax rate	-	30%
Insurance and local taxes	% _{TPC} /y	2.0
Fixed Maintenance cost	% _{TPC} /y	2.5
Maintenance labor cost	% of maint. costs	40
Administrative and support cost	% of oper. & maint. costs	30
CO ₂ transport and storage costs	€/t _{CO2}	30
Electricity selling price	€/MWh _e	80
Electricity purchase price	€/MWh _e	110
Electricity purchase price (steel plant)	€/MWh _e	85
Coal price	€/GJ _{LHV}	3.0
RDF price	€/t _{RDF}	20
Wood pellet price	€/t _{WP}	85
Limestone price	€/t _{limestone}	15
Carbon tax	€/t _{CO2}	100
Biomass (steel plant)	€/t _{bio}	85

4.2.1 CaL for cement plants

From an economic perspective, the CAPEX evaluation has been updated based on the energy and mass balances derived from the newly developed model and using the reference calculation methodology defined in the previous D4.3. The total plant cost of the updated base case is estimated at 282.67 M€ (see Figure 19).

Total Plant Cost: 282.67M€

Figure 20: Distribution of the total plant costs and division of the total installation costs (base case).

The economic analysis has been conducted for all advanced cases and updated from D4.3 for the Base case. This update highlights the effects of the new cost estimates and the lower emissions associated with the Base case while also evaluating the impacts of modifications made to the advanced cases. The breakdown of the Cost of CO₂ Avoided (CCA) is presented in Table 28 and each item can be easily compared in Figure 21.

Table 28: Breakdown of the Cost of CO₂ Avoided (CCA) for the advanced cases.

	Unit of measurement	Base case	CPUr	TC600	TC550	HXS	Ca(OH) ₂	O ₂ electrolysis
Fuel (coal)	€/t _{CO2}	14.74	15.22	14.96	15.17	14.46	14.92	14.74
Electricity	€/t _{CO2}	10.53	8.91	10.08	9.67	10.94	11.51	-0.96
Transport and storage	€/t _{CO2}	36.59	37.49	36.83	37.04	36.33	36.86	36.59
Variable O&M	€/t _{CO2}	1.08	1.02	1.08	1.07	1.08	1.06	1.08
Fixed OPEX	€/t _{CO2}	19.19	19.17	19.40	19.69	18.88	19.17	11.13
CAPEX	€/t _{CO2}	27.69	28.65	28.86	29.35	27.99	28.52	10.12
Cost of CO₂ avoided	€/t_{CO2}	110.63	110.46	111.21	112.00	109.68	112.04	78.07
ΔCOC	€/t_{clk}	39.97	41.87	40.31	40.60	39.75	41.59	21.82
Total Plant Cost	M€	282.67	303.91	288.22	293.78	277.97	288.17	149.40

Figure 21: Cost breakdown of the Cost of CO₂ avoided.

The configuration that recirculates the CPU vent gas into the carbonator results in the highest total plant cost due to the increased size of the carbonator, as illustrated in Figure 21. However, this configuration also achieves a higher capture rate and greater electricity production from heat recovery, leading to a marginally lower CCA.

Reducing the carbonator's temperature increases fuel expenditures because of the higher flow rate of circulating sorbent (see Figure 20). Conversely, the electricity costs decrease due to increased production from heat recovery in the carbonator. Therefore, targeting a lower carbonator temperature and a higher carbonation rate slightly raises both the CCA and total plant costs by 1.9%.

Introducing a heat exchanger between the calciner and the carbonator reduces fuel costs by 1.9%, allowing for a higher calciner feed temperature. However, this configuration increases electricity costs by 3.8% due to decreased recoverable heat from the carbonator. Consequently, the CCA is the lowest among the advanced cases, excluding the case with oxygen from electrolysis.

Finally, the configuration that involves injecting Ca(OH)₂ results in higher electricity costs due to reduced heat recovery and a higher TPC from adding a hydrator to convert the CaL purge to Ca(OH)₂ and increasing the sizes of the ASU and calciner. As a result, the CCA is higher than in the base case.

Figure 22: CCA and TPC of the advanced cases.

The final advanced case (O₂ electrolysis) explores the feasibility of feeding the calciner with oxygen produced as a by-product of water electrolysis, assuming there is no associated purchase cost. This approach eliminates the need for an ASU, and since the oxygen production system represents about 30% of the total installed cost (see Figure 20), the TPC for this scenario decreases significantly by 47%. Additionally, since the ASU is the primary electricity consumer, this configuration allows the plant to export electricity to the grid, thanks to the production of the HRSC associated with the CaL system, resulting in an additional negative contribution to the CCA value.

However, it is important to note that freely available oxygen requires specific conditions, such as the presence of electrolysis systems near the cement plant. According to values reported in the literature (Badgett et al., 2024), assuming a specific electricity consumption of 55.3 kWh_e/kg_{H₂} and an investment cost of 975 \$/kW_e, the necessary size of the electrolyzer is estimated to be 280 MW_e, with an installation cost of approximately 740 M€. In contrast, the purchasing price of oxygen needed to achieve the same CCA value as the base case is estimated to be 0.12 €/kg_{O₂}.

4.2.2 CaL for waste to energy and bio-CHP plants

For the economic analysis of the WtE application, the same assumptions defined in D4.3 (summarized in Table 27) have been used. Given the fact that the CO₂ emissions of the integrated plant (WtE+CaL) are lower than the fossil CO₂ emissions of the WtE plant, all direct CO₂ emissions are assumed as of biogenic origin and therefore, not subjected to pay any carbon tax. Moreover, the fossil CO₂ emissions captured from the WtE flue gases are preventing the plant to pay the corresponding carbon tax, and so their capture effect is equivalent to a cash flow corresponding to the carbon tax price. The capture of the biogenic share of the CO₂ present in the WtE flue gases and generated in the combustion process of the RDF in the calciner is supposed to be valorized at the price of the carbon tax (i.e., the plant is generating carbon credits due to emissions negative on an atmosphere CO₂ balance). Following this assumptions, the avoided CO₂ in the CCA calculation is obtained as the sum of the fossil emissions of the reference WtE plant, plus the biogenic CO₂ sent to storage.

The economic analysis developed for the base case has been applied to all the advanced cases described in subsection 4.1.2 in order to estimate the impacts of the different modifications on each case. In this analysis, an additional case (Case CPUr oxy) was also considered, with the hypothesis that the oxygen demand of the calciner is provided as a by-product of water electrolysis for hydrogen production. The outcomes achieved are shown in Table 29 and in Figure 22, Figure 23, Figure 24 and Figure 25. The CCA was calculated assuming that gate fee remains unvaried (i.e., delta gate fee = 0 €/t_{MSW}), while the breakeven incremental gate fee is calculated assuming a carbon tax of 100 €/t_{CO₂}.

Table 29: Main economic results for CaL application to WtE plant evaluated for the different configurations studied.

	Unit of measurement	Base case	CPUr (reference case)	CPUr Ca(OH) ₂ opt 1	CPUr Ca(OH) ₂ opt 2	CPUr TC 550	CPUr HXS	CPUr TC 550 HXS	Combined	CPUr oxy
Fuel (RDF)	€/t _{CO₂}	10.63	10.57	11.81	13.07	11.55	9.57	9.96	10.88	10.57
Limestone	€/t _{CO₂}	3.14	3.10	10.00	9.63	2.85	3.20	2.99	7.69	3.10
CO ₂ transport & storage	€/t _{CO₂}	48.03	47.92	54.46	56.08	49.12	46.56	46.94	53.10	47.92
Total Variable OPEX	€/t _{CO₂}	61.80	61.60	76.27	78.78	63.52	59.33	59.88	71.67	61.60
Electricity	€/t _{CO₂}	-28.39	-28.28	-20.96	-29.25	-33.43	-23.58	-25.82	-21.52	-43.58
Fixed OPEX	€/t _{CO₂}	39.97	36.56	36.10	39.30	39.63	34.40	36.44	36.61	25.56
CAPEX	€/t _{CO₂}	46.29	42.60	42.31	46.34	46.59	39.85	42.54	42.72	29.14
Cost of CO ₂ avoided	€/t _{CO₂}	128.33	120.44	141.64	143.84	125.02	117.45	121.00	137.48	78.16
Δ GATE FEE Breakeven	€/t _{MSW}	29.39	26.01	60.51	67.93	35.75	21.20	27.80	49.03	-27.79
Total Installed Cost	M€	295.55	333.93	378.14	442.98	411.47	297.59	347.25	343.63	225.12
Total Plant Cost	M€	473.42	534.58	606.27	708.18	656.55	477.36	555.47	551.10	365.64

Figure 23: Cost of avoided CO₂ and Breakeven incremental gate fee for CaL application to WtE plant evaluated for the different configurations studied.

Case CPUr, compared to the base case, presents a higher total plant cost and OPEX primarily due to the increase in the size of the various components. However, when considering the specific costs divided into the amount CO₂ avoided (see Table 29), an opposite trend is observed. This is mainly due to the improved CO₂ capture efficiency achieved by recycling the CPU vent gases into the carbonator, which consequently leads to higher avoided emissions and a lower Cost of Avoided CO₂ (-6.15%).

The CAPEX, OPEX, and CCA obtained for case CPUr Ca(OH)₂ opt 1, i.e., the configuration combining vent gas recirculation with the injection of Ca(OH)₂ into a duct downstream of the carbonator, are significantly higher compared to the case CPUr. It is worth noting that a factor with a significant impact on these estimates is the increase in limestone consumption related to the rise in the F₀/F_{CO₂} ratio to produce the necessary Ca(OH)₂. The in-situ production of hydrated lime requires a higher consumption of limestone and fuel (for its calcination), and consequently bigger components. Another consequence of the production of Ca(OH)₂, which affects the increase in CCA compared to Case 1 (+17.6%), is the reduction of the electricity production, due to the energy expenditure required to calcine the Ca(OH)₂, produce oxygen, and purify CO₂.

The outcomes achieved for case CPUr Ca(OH)₂ opt 2, which differs from the previous case because Ca(OH)₂ is injected directly in the upper part of the carbonator, follow the same trend as those described for case CPUr Ca(OH)₂ opt 1. The lower temperature in the carbonator leads to a further increase in fuel consumption and net electrical production. This results in an increase of both OPEX and CAPEX. The higher income related to electricity export is not sufficient to overcome this cost increase. Consequently, as clearly visible from the diagrams shown in Figure 22, Figure 23, Figure 24, and Figure 25, this configuration represents the worst-case scenario, as it yields the highest values of TPC, OPEX, and CCA.

Figure 24: Cost breakdown for the Cost of CO₂ Avoided for CaL application to WtE plant evaluated for the different configurations studied.

Due to the operating temperature decrease inside the carbonator (effects described previously), case CPUr TC 550 is characterized by higher RDF consumption, higher electricity production, and higher CCR compared to case CPUr. From an economic perspective, this implies that the CAPEX and OPEX are higher, but also the income for electricity production increases. This two effects counterbalance, and the CCA is slightly higher than Case 1 (+3,8%). Thanks to the solid regenerative pre-heating and to the consequent fuel saving, case CPUr HXS is characterized by lower CAPEX and OPEX with respect to case CPUr. As a consequence, the CCA decreases by 2.5% compared to case CPUr and by 8.5% compared to the Base Case.

Figure 25: Total plant cost for CaL application to WtE plant evaluated for the different configurations studied.

Figure 26: Total installed cost for CaL application to WtE plant evaluated for the different configurations studied. For cases 2, 3, and 7, the cost of the hydrator was also considered, while for cases 5, 6, and 7, the cost of the solid heat exchangers was taken into account.

The economic parameters characterizing case CPUr TC 550 HXS, which features the same configuration as case CPUr HXS except for the operating temperature of the carbonator, are similar to those obtained for case CPUr due to the combined effect of the modifications made. Variable OPEX are slightly lower (thanks to the fuel saving), TPC is higher (+3.91%) due to the cost of the solid heat exchangers, but as the amount of avoided CO₂ is higher, the CAPEX expressed in €/t_{CO2} is almost unvaried. Overall, the CCA differ by only +0.46%, compared to case CPUr.

Case Combined includes all the modifications applied to the base configuration. The combined impact of these modifications results in an increase in the CCA and in TPC (+14.15%, +3.09%, respectively) with respect to case CPUr. In case CPUr oxy, as mentioned at the beginning of this subsection, it is assumed that the oxygen requirement of the calciner is provided as a by-product of water electrolysis for hydrogen production. This approach removes the cost of the ASU, which results in a much lower TPC (-31.6%) and in a drastic increase in the income related to electricity export compared to case CPUr (43.58 vs 28.28 €/t_{CO2}), leading to a strong reduction CCA (-35.10%). However, it is important to note that freely available oxygen requires specific conditions, such as the presence of electrolysis systems near the WtE plant.

Regarding the economic analysis of the Bio-CHP application, it is assumed that wood pellet will be used as fuel for both the calciner and the main boiler. Its cost is assumed to be 85 €/t_{WP} and, as in the WtE application case, the cost of limestone is assumed to be 15 €/t_{limestone}. As explained previously, given the biogenic origin of the CO₂ generated from the combustion of both the main fuel and the calciner fuel, it is expected that the CO₂ captured and sent to storage will be valued at the carbon tax price (i.e., the plant is generating carbon credits due to negative emissions in the atmospheric CO₂ balance).

The main results obtained for each case investigated are summarized in Table 30 and shown in Figure 26, Figure 27, Figure 28, and Figure 29. As with the WtE, for the Bio-CHP, the case was also considered in which the oxygen demand of the calciner is supplied as a by-product of water electrolysis for hydrogen production (Case CPU_r oxy). The CCA was calculated assuming that electricity price remains unvaried (i.e. delta electricity price = 0 €/MWh), while the breakeven incremental electricity price is calculated assuming a carbon tax of 100 €/t_{CO2}.

Table 30: Main economic results for CaL application to Bio-CHP plant evaluated for the different configurations studied.

	Unit of measurement	Base case	CPU _r (reference case)	CPU _r Ca(OH) ₂	CPU _r TC 550	CPU _r HXS	CPU _r TC 550 HXS	Combined	CPU _r oxy
Fuel (pellet)	€/t _{CO2}	25.25	25.22	28.56	26.67	23.43	24.29	26.83	25.22
Limestone	€/t _{CO2}	1.96	1.95	7.19	1.75	2.07	1.90	5.55	1.95
CO ₂ transport & storage	€/t _{CO2}	31.72	31.71	36.33	31.54	31.82	31.68	36.09	31.71
Total Variable OPEX	€/t _{CO2}	58.93	58.88	72.08	59.96	57.33	57.87	68.47	58.88
Electricity	€/t _{CO2}	-19.42	-19.24	-13.82	-21.57	-16.63	-18.11	-14.97	-28.03
Fixed OPEX	€/t _{CO2}	40.04	35.78	34.58	36.23	35.56	35.92	36.20	26.88
CAPEX	€/t _{CO2}	44.69	40.16	39.22	41.15	39.60	40.41	40.80	29.26
Cost of CO ₂ avoided	€/t _{CO2}	132.60	123.09	139.39	123.46	123.26	123.65	138.12	92.46
Δ Electricity price Breakeven	€/t _{MSW}	34.37	27.63	57.81	29.65	27.37	29.31	50.10	-7.97
Total Installed cost	M€	173.60	184.90	210.78	216.63	168.81	190.91	194.43	132.93
Total Plant Cost	M€	279.01	297.32	339.70	347.48	271.85	306.81	313.30	216.63

Figure 27: Cost of avoided CO₂ and Breakeven incremental electricity price for CaL application to Bio-CHP plant evaluated for the different configurations studied.

Figure 28: Cost breakdown for the Cost of CO₂ Avoided for CaL application to Bio-CHP plant evaluated for the different configurations studied.

Figure 29: Total plant cost for CaL application to Bio-CHP plant evaluated for the different configurations studied.

Figure 30: Total installed cost for CaL application to Bio-CHP plant evaluated for the different configurations studied. For cases 2, 3, and 7, the cost of the hydrator was also considered, while for cases 5, 6, and 7, the cost of the solid heat exchangers was taken into account.

4.2.3 CaL for steel plants

For the EAF application, it is assumed to employ residual biomass as the fuel for the calciner, and its cost is assumed to be 85 €/t_{biomass} (~5 €/GJ_{LHV}) (S2Biom, 2025), limestone cost is assumed as 15 €/t_{CaCO₃} (Astolfi et al., 2019). It is assumed that all CO₂ emissions from the integrated EAF-CaL system (i.e., CO₂ in CO₂-lean gas from the carbonator and CPU vent gas) are of biogenic origin (being the residual ones not captured from biomass combustion in the calciner) and, therefore, not subjected to any carbon tax. Moreover, the fossil CO₂ emissions captured from the EAF off-gases prevent the plant from paying the corresponding carbon tax (assumed as 100 €/t_{CO₂}). So, their capture effect is equivalent to a cash flow corresponding to the carbon tax price. Furthermore, the CO₂ from the biomass combustion in the calciner is supposed to be valued at the price of the carbon tax (i.e., the plant is generating and

selling carbon credits due to its share of negative emissions, equivalent to a CO₂ removal from atmosphere's CO₂ balance). The cost of electricity and CO₂ transport and storage are assumed to be 85 €/MWh (Eurostat, 2025) and 30 €/t_{CO2}, respectively.

The Total Plant Cost (TPC) for each case is presented in Figure 31. When comparing the advanced cases against the standard cases, it can be seen that the CPU's TPC is higher in the advanced cases due to the higher CO₂ processing capacity (see Table 26). For the same reason, ASU's TPC is higher due to the increased oxygen consumption. On the other hand, the variation in the TPC of the CaL section and the steam cycle is much lower.

Additionally, when comparing cases with intermediate solid storage against those without solid storage, the results indicate that including this strategy reduces the total TPC by ~19%. The most considerable TPC reductions are obtained for the CPU and CaL sections due to the smaller gas holder for CO₂-rich gas and calciner capacities, respectively, while also the cost of the CaL reactors is reduced by around 15 M€.

Finally, the steel cost increment and the cost of CO₂ avoided are presented in Figure 31. Cases with intermediate solid storage resulted in lower steel cost increments (27-30 €/t_{steel}). Such a result is attributed to the lower CAPEX required for those cases. On the other hand, including the advanced strategies (i.e., Ca(OH)₂ injection and CPU vent gas recirculation) led to slightly higher steel cost increments since, in these cases, the higher CAPEX and OPEX are partially balanced with the increased revenues from carbon tax and credits due to the higher CO₂ capture rate. Regarding the cost of CO₂ avoided, the results indicate that implementing the advanced strategies is beneficial. Furthermore, the combination of the advanced strategies and intermediate solid storages resulted to be the most advantageous configuration since it led to the lowest CCA value of 205 €/t_{CO2}.

Figure 31: Total Plant Cost break-down for CaL application to EAF plant for the different plant configurations analyzed.

a) Steel cost increment

b) Cost of CO₂ avoided

Figure 32: Cost breakdown for a) steel cost increment and b) for the Cost of CO₂ Avoided (CCA). They were computed taking into account the fact that the EAF-CaL integrated plant is reaching negative net emissions due to the biogenic carbon content in the biomass used as fuel in the calciner. The category "Others" comprises workforce, maintenance, insurance, and taxes expenditures.

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